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6G Goal-Oriented **AI**-enabled **L**earning and **S**emantic Communication Networks
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Deliverable D3.2

Semantic data acquisition, representation
and compression methodologies: First results

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the initial results of the 6G-GOALS project in the context of semantic data acquisition, representation, and compression methodologies. It marks a significant step toward realizing the vision of goal-oriented and AI-native communication in future semantic 6G networks. In the first part, the focus is placed on developing learning-based and topology-aware approaches for data representation, leveraging advanced techniques such as graph neural networks, knowledge graphs, and diffusion models. The deliverable further introduces innovative semantic compression schemes, including opportunistic and reinforcement learning-driven methods tailored to communication environments with stringent latency and efficiency constraints. In the second part, semantic data acquisition strategies are also explored, targeting practical scenarios such as multimodal sensing and opportunistic sampling. These results serve as foundational components for a holistic 6G semantic communication system where information is processed, transmitted, and interpreted according to its relevance to predefined goals.

Keywords

6G Networks; Semantic Communication; Goal-Oriented Communication; Semantic Representation Learning; Graph Neural Networks; Topological Deep Learning; Knowledge Graphs; Semantic Compression; Diffusion Models; Reinforcement Learning; Adaptive Transformers; Multimodal Sensing; Radio-based Sensing; AI-native Communication; Task-driven Information Processing

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

6G	Sixth-Generation
ACGAN	Attention-based Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks
AE	AutoEncoder
AVE	Audio-Visual Event
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
BAA	Blahut-Arimoto Algorithm
BEV	Bird's Eye View
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
CC	Cell Complex
CCA	Canonical Correlation Analysis
CCNN	Cell Complex Neural Network
CGAN	Conditional Generative Adversarial Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CP	Collaborative Perception
CSI	Channel State Information
DCM	Differentiable Cell Module
DGM	Differentiable Graph Module
DiffCP	Diffusion model based Collaborative Perception
DP	Dynamic Programming
DTW	Dynamic Time Warping
E2E	End-to-End
FFN	Feed-Forward Network
FIFO	First-In-First-Out
FLOP	FLoating Point Operations
FPS	Frames Per Second
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GRL	Graph Representation Learning
GSP	Graph Signal Processing
IoU	Intersection-over-Union
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
IUS	Intelligent Unmanned System
JSCC	Joint Source-Channel Coding
KG	Knowledge Graph
LLM	Large Language Model
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MFCC	Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficient
MINE	Mutual Information Neural Estimation
MJPEG	Motion Joint Photographic Experts Group
MLP	MultiLayer Perceptron
MP	Message Passing
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NN	Neural Network
PIM	Polygon Inference Module
PSV	Probability of Simultaneity Violation
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RTP	Real-time Transport Protocol
RTT	Round-Trip Time
RV	Random Variable
SemCom	Semantic Communication

SE	Semantic Extractor
SPIRIT	Streaming Pattern Discovery in Multiple Time-Series
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TDL	Topological Deep Learning
TDoA	Time Difference of Arrival
TWI	Temporal Window of Integration
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications
UWB	Ultra-Wideband
ViT	Vision Transformer
IoU	Intersection over Union

1 Introduction

The vision of the 6G-GOALS project is to radically reshape the landscape of wireless communications by embracing a goal-oriented and semantic-first paradigm [SDS+24]. Rather than focusing solely on the accurate delivery of bits, future 6G systems are envisioned to prioritize the transmission of meaningful, context-aware information that directly supports specific tasks and application goals. This shift is necessitated by the increasing demand for intelligent and resource-efficient communication systems that can support mission-critical applications such as collaborative robotics, digital twins, autonomous systems, and real-time decision-making processes.

Building upon the theoretical foundations established in Deliverable D3.1 and the system-level requirements and scenarios outlined in Deliverable D2.3, this deliverable (D3.2) provides the first concrete implementation results related to the semantic processing pipeline — from the initial sensing and data acquisition stages, through representation and compression, to their impact on downstream communication and inference tasks.

At its core, Deliverable D3.2 aims to demonstrate how semantic awareness — defined here as the ability to extract, interpret, compress, and utilize only the information necessary to achieve predefined goals — can be embedded within communication protocols and machine learning models. This aligns with the overall ambition of the 6G-GOALS project: to enable a network of intelligence, where agents and devices interact not just by exchanging raw data, but by collaboratively understanding and acting upon semantically-relevant signals.

1.1 Scope and contributions

This deliverable presents early but significant advancements in three core areas that underpin semantic communication (SemCom) within 6G:

- **Semantic Representation Learning:** leveraging Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), higher-order topological models, and Knowledge Graphs (KGs) to capture structured semantic relations and enable robust, goal-driven feature representations.
- **Semantic Compression:** introducing novel mechanisms for reducing data size while maintaining semantic utility, including methods based on diffusion models, reinforcement learning, and adaptive transformers.
- **Semantic Data Acquisition:** proposing sensing strategies and data sampling methods that prioritize information based on its relevance to the system's objectives, with a focus on multimodal, radio-based, and distributed sensing setups.

The contribution of this deliverable is both methodological and empirical: we not only introduce new frameworks and algorithms, but also provide initial evaluation results demonstrating their viability in constrained communication scenarios.

These developments pave the way for a unified SemCom stack, enabling intelligent and context-aware information exchange, while optimizing key 6G performance metrics such as latency, bandwidth, and energy consumption.

1.2 Organization of the document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces representation learning techniques for SemCom, focusing on graph-based methods, latent topology inference, and KG integration.

- Section 3 details the semantic compression strategies, including distributed diffusion-based approaches, reinforcement learning for task-driven compression, and adaptive token selection using transformers.
- Section 4 explores semantic data acquisition mechanisms, including sampling for goal-oriented communication, radio-based sensing, and multimodal data forecasting.
- Section 5 summarizes the main findings, highlights the importance of semantic-aware system design, and outlines future research directions.

Each section contains both the theoretical framework and the experimental results that validate the proposed methodologies. Together, they form a comprehensive view of the state-of-the-art in semantic processing within the context of the 6G-GOALS project.

2 Representation learning for semantic communication

SemCom transcends the paradigm of conventional communication by prioritizing the conveyance of semantic content over mere bit stream transmission. Indeed, while traditional communication systems are concerned with the technical tier of message exchange, SemCom endeavours to operate within the semantic tier, encoding the meaning of information at the semantic encoder and interpreting an equivalent matching meaning at the semantic decoder [KP21]. This approach to communication notably enhances the efficiency of distilling data for transmission and it improves the resilience against noise of the communication process. In this section, we focus on graph-based, knowledge-based, and sheaf-based representation learning techniques for SemCom, respectively in Section 2.1, Section 2.2, and Section 2.3.

2.1 Latent topology inference

2.1.1 Graph neural networks and latent graph inference

When working with neural networks (NNs), a major issue is how best to represent and manipulate data – as different representations can provide significantly different results (as further described later in Section 3.3, in the context of token-based communication systems). As the focus of this section, in multiple scenarios the data to be acquired and communicated possess a graph structure, in which constituting elements are associated by pairwise relations. This is the case, e.g., for biochemical data, social networks, energy grids, or point clouds. Graph neural networks (GNNs) are a class of trainable models customized for operating on graph-based data that can be trained to perform a variety of tasks, including but not limited to node or edge classification, graph generation, and graph anomaly detection. These are generally designed on a message-passing (MP) paradigm, in which nodes and edges exchange trainable messages on the basis of the underlying connectivity. This is part of a broader framework known as graph representation learning (GRL, [BBL+17]).

A **graph** can be represented as a pair of sets \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E} , where $\mathcal{V} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the set of **nodes** (vertices), and $\mathcal{E} = \{(i, j) : i, j \in \mathcal{V}\}$ is a set of edges connecting the nodes (which can, equivalently, be described in the form of an adjacency matrix). A **graph signal** is a function associating to each node a vector-valued representation:

$$\mathbf{x}_i : \mathcal{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^F.$$

We call \mathbf{x}_i the node features or node embeddings depending on context. A generic MP layer updates the embeddings by propagating them according to the neighbourhood of each node:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \gamma \left(\mathbf{x}_i \oplus \bigoplus_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \phi(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) \right),$$

where γ and ϕ are trainable layers (e.g., multilayer perceptrons, MLPs), \oplus is a permutation-invariant operation (e.g., mean or sum), and $\mathcal{N}(i)$ is the neighbourhood of node i , i.e., the set of edges having at least one vertex in common with node i . A GNN is built as the concatenation

of one or more MP layers. Different types of MP layers can be obtained by suitably varying the type of features and/or connectivity. For example, various edge-based MP layers can be designed by defining the neighbourhood of an edge as the pair of edges they connect [IGR21].

In the context of goal-oriented communications, a major drawback of GNN models is the assumption that the input graph is known and fixed a-priori. In many cases, this might not be true, either because the graph is inadequate for the task at hand (as in the case of heterophilic datasets, explored in Section 2.1.4), or because the graph itself is (completely or partially) unknown. In these cases, the graph must be inferred automatically from the node feature matrix. In some specific situations, this can be achieved with simple distance-based heuristic, as in point cloud networks. More generally, **latent graph inference** methods can be used to learn the graph in an end-to-end fashion together with the MP layers. In particular, the **differentiable graph module** (DGM) [KCA+22] learns a separate node-wise embedding, such that the distance between the embeddings is proportional to the probability of the edge appearing in the graph. Then, a differentiable sampling operation is used to obtain the output graph, based on the product distribution of these probabilities. In DGM, the graph can change from layer to layer by adding multiple DGM blocks. However, it is limited to sampling *regular* graphs, in which nodes are connected to a set of k other nodes, with k fixed beforehand.

2.1.2 Cell complex representation learning

All the methods described in Section 0 are built on the assumption that pairwise relations are a valid representation of the underlying connectivity. However, in many scenarios multi-way relations are also present, such as functional groups in molecules or “is-family” relations in knowledge bases. Decomposing multi-way relations into separate pairwise relations risks losing relevant information and reducing the effectiveness of the data. For these reasons, extensions of GNNs to handle higher-order data have been proposed under the framework of **topological deep learning** (TDL) [PBB+24].

In the context of goal-oriented communications, TDL faces three main challenges. The first is finding a valid representation for the higher-order relations, similar to the use of graphs for pairwise relations. The second is extending the MP paradigm to take into account this new class of relations in order to optimize for tasks defined at multiple levels (e.g., classification over functional groups). Finally, we require extensions of latent graph inference methods for scenarios in which the multi-way relations are unknown or partially hidden. We note that the last point is even more critical than in the graph case, since there is a scarcity of datasets in the field, as we highlighted in a recent position paper [PBB+24]. Fixed heuristics to build a higher-order network purely from nodes and edges, known as graph liftings, are generally insufficient from an empirical point of view, limiting the effectiveness of TDL methods [HPF+24].

To solve these three tasks, this subsection describes **latent topology inference**, a framework recently introduced in [BST+24] which provides a *trainable* mechanism to jointly learn the underlying algebraic topology of the data together with the task-oriented neural network model. As shown later, this significantly improves over fixed lifting-based heuristics, especially when the provided graph does not match with the task at hand. In particular, we describe a specific implementation of the framework, called **differentiable cell module** (DCM), built on a cell complex representation of the higher-order connectivity. This is shown schematically in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: High-level overview of the DCM framework.

Cell complexes (CC) are topological spaces that are built by the combination of multiple topological spaces of variable “dimensionality”, whose components are called *cells*. They can be thought of as generalizing graphs as nodes and edges correspond to cells of dimensions 0 and 1, respectively (0-cells and 1-cells). In DCM we also learn a collection of 2-cells \mathcal{P} , which are collections of cycles induced by the underlying edges. The triplet $\{\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{P}\}$ then defines a CC. This is an informal definition of CC that is sufficient for our description, while we refer to [BST+24] for the complete definition.

2.1.3 Overview of the DCM algorithm

Trivially extending DGM to the sampling of 2-cells would incur a significant computational overhead, as the number of possible polygons grows exponentially in their size. DCM overcomes this issue by a 2-step procedure, schematically shown in Figure 2-3. Given a set of nodes (with corresponding node features) we first process them by an extension of DGM that we call α -DGM, which allows to sample a non-regular graph in a trainable way (called the **skeleton**). This step can be conditioned with an existing graph (either coming from the input or from a previous DCM block). Next, a **polygon inference module** (PIM) samples a set of 2-cells, only considering those that are allowed by the previously inferred skeleton. The output of the procedure is a complete CC, which is then processed by a series of MP layers customized for cell complexes. We provide below a brief description of the three components, skipping some non-essential details for brevity (e.g., layer normalization).

α -DGM: denote by $\mathbf{x}_0(i)$ the node features (where we add a 0 to distinguish them from the edge and polygon features to be introduced later). First, these are embedded in a new space by a trainable projection $\mathbf{x}_{0,aux}(i) = v_0(\mathbf{x}_0(i))$. As in DGM, the probability that an edge is sampled in the output graph is proportional to $p_{ij} = s(\mathbf{x}_{0,aux}(i), \mathbf{x}_{0,aux}(j))$, where s is some pre-specified distance function (e.g., a Gaussian kernel). Instead of the softmax normalization employed in DGM, we normalize these values with an α -entmax operation [PNM19], keeping an edge only if the post-processed value is larger than 0. This provides a non-regular output graph, whose level of sparsity can be controlled by the user (or learned) by modifying the α parameter of the entmax function [PNM19]. The output of this step is the inferred skeleton of the CC.

Before proceeding, three sets of embeddings are computed based on the inferred skeleton. First, the original input features $\mathbf{x}_0(i)$ are processed with a standard GNN block to obtain a preliminary set of node-wise updated features $\mathbf{x}_{0,out}(i)$. Second, for each edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ of the inferred skeleton, edge features $\mathbf{x}_{1,out}(i)$ are obtained by an “uplifting” module that combines the node features $\mathbf{x}_{0,out}(i)$ and $\mathbf{x}_{0,out}(j)$, which are used as input to a cell complex neural network (CCNN) block [HIZ20]), an MP layer customized to work with CCs. Third, auxiliary edge features $\mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(i)$ for each edge are computed with a separate trainable projection from the input features $\mathbf{x}_{0,aux}(i)$ and $\mathbf{x}_{0,aux}(j)$, which are used instead in the PIM block.

PIM: In a symmetric fashion with respect to the graph sampling step, we use the auxiliary embeddings $\mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(i)$ to sample 2-cells. In particular, we first extract all possible 2-cells (up to a maximum length fixed by the user) supported by the underlying skeleton. To each of these cells we associate a probability given by the sum of all edge probabilities. For example, suppose we identify a cell composed of edges $(i, j), (j, k), (k, i)$. The associated probability of being sampled is given by:

$$s(\mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(i), \mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(j)) + s(\mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(j), \mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(k)) + s(\mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(k), \mathbf{x}_{1,aux}(i)).$$

Finally, we apply a second α -entmax operation on the full set of 2-cells probabilities to sample a smaller subset. The output of this operation is a complete CC specification.

CCNN: the last block computes the final updated node embeddings based on the inferred CC. In particular, the updated edge features $x_{1,out}(i)$, together with the inferred 2-cells, are processed by a trainable CCNN. The output of the CCNNs is then downlifted at the node level (by an additional MP operation), and the output is concatenated to the features $x_{0,out}(i)$ computed by the previous GNN block before being processed by a final trainable block.

This setup returns updated node embeddings which are suitable for, e.g., node classification tasks. It can be easily modified to handle other tasks (e.g., edge classification) by returning the intermediate edge or cell features in output.

2.1.4 Experimental evaluation

We evaluate the DCM module on a series of challenging graph benchmark tasks, where we either refine the original graph structure or discard it completely to let the model learn a proper CC from scratch. We perform experiments both in a homophilic scenario (similar nodes tend to be connected in the graph) and heterophilic scenarios (dissimilar nodes tend to be connected in the graph). We report here the results in the heterophilic case for brevity, as the results in the homophilic case are similar. We use the Texas, Wisconsin, Squirrel, and Chameleon datasets from [RAS21]. For the details of the architecture and training process, we refer to Appendix E in [BST+24] and the online repository.¹ The complete neural network model is composed of an initial embedding layer, followed by a DCM module, while the GNN and CCNN inside the DCM module are composed of one graph convolutional layer and one cell convolutional layer, respectively. All baselines share a similar architecture in terms of trainable parameters.

We consider as baselines a DGM model and a DGM variant proposed in [DKB+23] which exploits non-Euclidean geometries for computing the similarity embeddings, representing the state-of-the-art for latent graph inference at the time of writing. We also consider a variant of DCM where the second entmax step is skipped and all cells from the inferred skeleton are used (referred to as $\alpha=1$ below).

		Texas	Wisconsin	Squirrel	Chameleon
	Model/Hom. level	0.11	0.21	0.22	0.23
w/o graph	MLP	77.78 ± 10.24	85.33 ± 4.99	30.44 ± 2.55	40.35 ± 3.37
	DGM-E [11]	80.00 ± 8.31	88.00 ± 5.65	34.35 ± 2.34	48.90 ± 3.61
	DGM-M [12]	81.67 ± 7.05	89.33 ± 1.89	35.00 ± 2.35	48.90 ± 3.61
	DCM	85.71 ± 7.87	87.49 ± 5.94	35.55 ± 2.24	53.63 ± 3.07
	DCM ($\alpha = 1$)	84.96 ± 10.24	86.72 ± 6.02	35.25 ± 2.22	53.67 ± 3.19
w graph	GCN	41.66 ± 11.72	47.20 ± 9.76	24.19 ± 2.56	32.56 ± 3.53
	DGM-E [11]	60.56 ± 8.03	70.67 ± 10.49	29.87 ± 2.46	44.19 ± 3.85
	DGM-M [12]	62.78 ± 9.31	76.00 ± 3.26	30.44 ± 2.38	45.68 ± 2.66
	DCM	84.87 ± 10.04	86.33 ± 5.14	34.95 ± 2.59	53.05 ± 3.00
	DCM ($\alpha = 1$)	84.96 ± 5.60	85.36 ± 5.05	35.13 ± 2.27	53.76 ± 3.72

Figure 2-2: Experimental results of DCM (accuracy over node classification).

Results are shown in Figure 2-2, where the best result is highlighted in red, the second-best result is highlighted in blue, and all results are averaged over 10 trials. It can be seen that the DCM model achieves significantly better results in all scenarios. The gain in performance is especially large when considering the input graph as given since, in a heterophilic case, the graph is misaligned to the task at hand and the MP layers are penalized. Hence, the DCM block is able to adaptively select the good parts of the given graph in a task-driven manner.

To validate this insight, we show in Figure 2-3 the evolution of the graph connectivity (with edges shown in purple and triangles shown in orange) on the Texas dataset, together with a measure

¹ https://github.com/spindro/differentiable_cell-complex_module

of homophily (denoted as h). The fact that most of the inferred polygons belong to the same class and the high spread of the degree distribution further confirm the effectiveness of the proposed architecture.

Figure 2-3: Evolution of the connectivity in the Texas dataset, together with the associated degree distribution and homophily level (h).

2.1.5 Conclusions

In this section, we explored the challenges and solutions associated with learning latent topological structures in goal-oriented communication systems. Beginning with traditional GNNs and their reliance on fixed, often suboptimal input graphs, we highlighted the need for end-to-end latent graph inference methods. We then extended this framework to accommodate higher-order relations using the differentiable cell module (DCM), which enables the joint learning of both the graph skeleton and multi-way relations in the form of cell complexes. The modular structure of DCM—combining α -DGM, polygon inference, and CCNN layers—offers a flexible and scalable solution for topology-aware learning. Experimental results confirm that DCM significantly outperforms existing methods, particularly in heterophilic settings, by selectively refining or replacing the input structure in a task-driven manner. This demonstrates the potential of latent topology inference as a powerful paradigm for structure-aware learning in complex communication scenarios.

2.2 Semantic communication enhanced by knowledge graph representation learning

2.2.1 Knowledge graphs

In the previous section, we focused on data represented by generic multiway relations having no specific type (meaning) attached to them. We now consider instead information extracted from data that is semantically represented in Knowledge Graphs (KGs), formed by nodes (entities) and typed edges (relationships).

KGs provide structured representations of knowledge, organized into triples in the form of node-relationship-node, enabling the incorporation of semantic meaning into data. Thus, knowledge is structured and semantic messages selected, pragmatically aligning with the source’s intent or the destination’s objective and context, or serving a specific goal [SDS+24]. Recent works propose SemCom systems based on KGs where semantic symbols are represented in the form

of node-relationship-node triples for semantic extraction and interpretation [HLZ+22]. Those works mainly attempt to enhance accuracy, dispel interpretation ambiguities, improve data compression efficacy at the source, and enhance error correction robustness at the destination. Notably, [JLZ+22] delineates an approach where transmission is adaptively modulated in response to channel quality, with a priority transmission accorded to semantically significant triples. Concurrently, [ZLX+24] introduces a framework for cognitive SemCom tailored to both single and multiple-user scenarios. In the current state of the art, when semantic information is extracted in the form of KGs, triples in the graphs are associated with semantic symbols to be transmitted. Thus, after (graph-based) semantic extraction, transmission signs (or patterns of signs) are optimized for transmission (semiotic [M14]), but without exploiting the embedded meaning in the semantic message which is captured in the graph structure.

2.2.2 Overview of the proposed methodology

In this section, we exploit the properties of the specific instance of the extracted graph such as its structure and descriptors of relations between nodes. We propose a novel End-to-End (E2E) pragmatic optimization SemCom framework, optimizing the transmitter, the latent space representation and compression, and the receiver [HDS24]. This is done by representing semantic messages in the form of pragmatically sparsified KGs, being relevant to the receiver given the locally available knowledge. To learn the semantic relevant KG representation in lower-dimension latent spaces, we propose to cascade a pre-trained Large Language Model (LLM) module that associates embeddings to source data, with a GNN module that processes the combined output from the LLM module with the available inherent graphs topologies of the data. Such graphs are either available within the dataset or can be extracted with LLMs [TST23]. The proposed semantic architecture encodes the KG in a batch of vectors, each one containing the semantic information about a node, the nodes connected to it, and the relations connecting them. The cardinality of such a batch of vectors encoding the graph is equal to the number of its nodes. Through this methodology, we numerically illustrate enhancements in both compression rates and communication robustness.

2.2.3 System model

The proposed architecture is shown in Figure 2-4 and detailed along this section. A KG is represented by a set of nodes, function of the textual attributes of the node, and by the relational structure amongst these nodes, function of the relational attributes of the link directed from the source node to the target node. The essential blocks of the system model are illustrated in the sequel.

Figure 2-4: System model of semantic representation learning on graphs

Semantic Encoders

The semantic encoder associates each node of the source KG to an embedding vector. We propose two semantic encoders named $Encllm_{gnn}$ and $Encllm_{ffn}$, respectively. In particular, $Encllm_{gnn}$ cascades a pre-trained LLM (Figure 2-4, block (a)) with a GNN (Figure 2-4(b)). The LLM is adept at distilling textual features, consequently, we apply these models to synthesize the initial feature vectors pertinent to the textual attributes associated with nodes and relations of the KG. Those vectors constitute the preliminary node and relations feature vectors within the GNN. Subsequently, the GNN is employed to synthesize node representations. This final representation is an amalgamation of textual and relational information pertinent to the node, encapsulating a comprehensive semantic representation. To be more specific, the LLM associates the initial features vectors with the descriptors of the node and the relation. Subsequently, the GNN generates a compact representation vector of the node by fusing the initial features of the neighbouring nodes and the initial features of the relations that culminate at the node. The intricate architecture of a KG, characterized by its attributed vertices and edges, necessitates the deployment of a GNN that must be adept at accommodating the inherent heterogeneity of the vertices, the directionality of the edges, and the rich feature representation of the edges. In this context, we exploit the graph isomorphism convolutional neural network in [HLG+20], an instance of a MP layer which reads as:

$$x'_i = h_\theta \left((1 + \epsilon) \cdot x_i + \sum_{j \in N(i)} \text{ReLU}(x_j + e_{j,i}) \right).$$

Here, x'_i is the output features vector of node i , h_θ is a sequential neural network, ϵ is a trainable value, x_i is the node i 's initial features vector, and $e_{j,i}$ are the features of the relational edge linking node j to node i .

The second proposed encoder is denoted as $Encllm_{ffn}$, and is composed by the cascade of a LLM with a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFN) bottleneck (Figure 2-4, block (c)). The aim of the FFN bottleneck step is to perform compression of the initial feature vector associated by the LLM to each node, but without taking into consideration the associative relationships in the KG. This aspect makes this encoder substantially different from the previous $Encllm_{gnn}$.

Channel Coding

The channel encoder consists of a FFN and a power normalization layer, modulating each low-dimensional vector from the semantic encoder into complex symbols. The channel decoder, using an FFN architecture, demodulates the received symbols back into the set of latent space vectors. We use mutual information to determine the optimal channel encoding function (Figure 2-4, block (d)) for an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) channel. The mutual information between the channel's input and output is approximated using the Mutual Information Neural Estimation (MINE) [BBR+18] framework.

Semantic Decoder

At the semantic decoder, the received message is decoded from a set of embedding vectors to infer a KG congruent with the one intended by the source. To infer the KG, we combine two decoding functions which separately classify the graph's nodes and their relations:

- **Nodes classifier** (Figure 2-4, block (e)): The node classification mechanism employs a deep architecture to categorize distinct decoded embedding vectors, attributing each to a specific node (i.e., semantic concept).
- **Relation classifier** (Figure 2-4, block (f)): The relation classifier works as a discerning mechanism to reconstruct the edges within the KG. It achieves this by utilizing node representations obtained from the graph encoder. Within this structure, combinations of embeddings are processed to associate commensurate relations.

2.2.4 Knowledge graph representation learning

Consider θ and ϑ as the respective trainable parameters of the semantic encoder and the semantic decoder. Drawing upon the insights of [SS22], the loss function used to train the system under consideration writes as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\theta,\vartheta}^{\text{CE}} - \alpha I_{\theta}(X; Y).$$

The function encapsulates the cross-entropy term augmented with a penalty parameter considering a weighted mutual information component, which reflects the interdependence between variables X and Y across the semantic channel from transmission to reception. The random variable g , intrinsic to a KG, manifests as the joint random variable outlining the stochastic properties of two independent random variables n (representing the nodes) and r (standing for the relations). Overall, we have two parallel components: one dedicated to the inference of nodes, and the other designated on establishing relations between them. Mathematically, this can be cast as the minimization of the following function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\theta,\vartheta}^{\text{CE},g} = \mathcal{L}_{\theta,\vartheta}^{\text{CE},n} + \mathcal{L}_{\theta,\vartheta}^{\text{CE},r}.$$

One training epoch in our framework consists of two steps: Step one involves the calibration of the mutual information estimation model. Then, step two encompasses training the entire E2E model using a dual-objective optimization strategy that combines cross-entropy loss minimization with mutual information maximization to improve predictive accuracy.

2.2.5 Experimental evaluation

We assess the performance of the proposed graph-based E2E wireless SemCom system via numerical simulation. On the transmitter side, KGs nodes are encoded into vectors of semantic embeddings, then each embedding vector is modulated into complex symbols to be transmitted over the AWGN channel. We compare the two encoder designs $Encllm_{gmn}$ and $Encllm_{ffn}$. At the receiver, KGs are inferred from the received (noisy) semantic symbols. We assess the decoder's fidelity with the F1 score metric, which measures the average equivalence of nodes and relations between the transmitted and the decoded KGs by checking the exact match of the inferred triple elements with the source triple elements.

In Figure 2-5 we compare the performance in terms of node classification accuracy versus the embedding compression at the output of the encoders under noiseless wireless channel conditions. Our numerical results show that for an embedding compression factor of 24 or greater, $Encllm_{gmn}$ exceed 98% of node classification accuracy and outperforms $Encllm_{ffn}$. Moreover, we observe that its performance slightly depends on the embedding size of the SemCom system, thanks to the inclusion of the graph topology information in $Encllm_{gmn}$.

In Figure 2-6, we illustrate instead the behaviour of the F1 score metric versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), considering an AWGN channel, and comparing the proposed encoders $Encllm_{gmn}$ and $Encllm_{ffn}$ with traditional encoding techniques: Huffman and 6-bits coding coupled with a 64-QAM modulation scheme. As we can notice, both proposed encoders perform closely the same in terms of F1 score, highlighting how a graph-based semantic encoding and decoding notably outperforms the traditional techniques in the low SNR regime.

In Figure 2-7, we present the transmitted information over the channel, measured as the average number of bits per KG, plotted against the number of nodes in the graph. The average compression gain factor for the two proposed semantic approaches is 5.54 compared to Huffman encoding, and 7.17 compared to 6-bits encoding.

Figure 2-5: Node classification accuracy vs. node embedding dimensionality.

Figure 2-6: F1 score of received and source KGs matching vs. SNR when dealing with AWGN channel.

2.2.6 Conclusions

In this section, we investigate the effectiveness of LLM and GNN based on encoders for semantic compression of KGs. To this end, we propose an E2E graph-based SemCom framework, aiming to embed KGs derived from data into low-dimensional latent space, thus optimizing the compression of knowledge representation.

We introduce a novel method for semantic encoding and decoding of KGs with two variants for semantic encoding, the first one based on GNNs exploiting the relational spectrum of nodes, while the second one based on FFN treating each node isolated without considering its neighbourhood.

Our numerical results validate the effectiveness of the proposed framework, reaching almost 99,5% and 94% of node classification accuracy for the two encoders respectively. In addition, we also observe how the proposed graph-based semantic encoding and decoding functions notably outperform traditional Huffman and 6-bits coding in the low-average SNR regime, requiring about 14 dBs less of SNR to reach their maximum F1 score in our simulation settings. In conclusion, through the proposed design, we realize enhancements in both compression rates and communication robustness.

Figure 2-7: Transmitted information in bits per graph versus the number of nodes in the graph.

2.3 Sheaf-theoretic semantic representation learning

2.3.1 Motivation

In modern signal processing and machine learning, a central and ongoing objective is to uncover hidden structures within data — structures that often reside not in traditional flat, Euclidean spaces, but rather in complex, non-Euclidean domains such as graphs, manifolds, and higher-dimensional topological spaces. Traditional tools assume that relationships among data points can be understood through simple metrics like the Euclidean distance; however, in many real-world systems — from social networks to sensor arrays and KGs — the relationships are far richer and demand more sophisticated representations. Within this context, Graph Signal Processing (GSP) has emerged as a powerful framework for modelling pairwise relationships inherent in structured datasets [DTT+20]. GSP generalizes classical signal processing concepts to the graph domain, providing elegant ways to define notions like frequency, filtering, and smoothness when data is supported on the nodes of a network. Nevertheless, the expressiveness of GSP is inherently limited: it primarily models interactions between pairs of nodes and struggles when faced with the need to represent higher-order interactions, non-uniform data domains, or more intricate topological features that are crucial for a true semantic understanding of the data (cf. Section 2.1).

To overcome these limitations and move towards truly semantic modelling, researchers have turned to sheaf theory — a powerful mathematical framework that extends graph-based models to more general topological spaces [MM12]. Sheaf theory provides a principled way to associate structured data (such as vector spaces or groups) to the elements of a topological space (like nodes, edges, or higher-dimensional faces) while enforcing consistency conditions across overlapping regions. In particular, a key operator in this framework, the sheaf Laplacian, plays a

central role: it not only captures the underlying topology of the space but also models how semantic information — in the form of data transformations called restriction maps — flows between connected elements.

While the classic graph Laplacian measures smoothness of signals over a simple graph by penalizing differences between connected nodes, the sheaf Laplacian generalizes this idea to much richer contexts. Each node and each edge in the structure carries its own data space, and the restriction maps describe how local pieces of information must relate, making the framework ideal for capturing semantic relationships that are not merely numeric but structurally meaningful.

In this sense, learning the sheaf Laplacian directly from data becomes a fundamental step in semantic representation learning. It allows one to infer not just which data points are related, but how their associated local spaces transform and align — thereby extracting both topological and geometric insights from raw observations. Once this inferred topology is available, it unlocks the possibility to design SemCom strategies that are tailored to the structure of the data itself. In contrast to traditional communication strategies that blindly transmit bits, SemCom aims to transmit only the information that is meaningful within a given context — a shift particularly relevant for future AI-native networks envisioned in initiatives like the 6G-GOALS project. However, despite the theoretical richness of sheaf theory, practical methods for learning sheaves from data have been relatively scarce. Early work such as [HG19] introduced optimization-based approaches to estimate sheaf Laplacians from observations. While these methods were elegant, they were also computationally heavy and, crucially, they did not recover the underlying restriction maps, meaning they could not fully specify the semantic transformations between local data spaces. As a result, these methods fell short of capturing the full expressive power of cellular sheaves. This gap motivates the need for a more efficient, scalable, and interpretable solution, capable of jointly learning both the topology and the detailed mechanisms (restriction maps) that govern the flow of semantic information across the structure. In the sequel, we propose such a solution, detailed in our publication [DBD24], offering a numerically efficient framework that opens the door to more meaningful semantic topological inference.

2.3.2 Methodology

We start introducing the concept of sheaves on graphs and to outline the mathematical apparatus that supports the formulation of the learning problem. At its heart, a sheaf can be seen as a way of associating structured data to a topological space in a manner that enforces local-to-global consistency. When working with graphs — which are discrete topological structures — this idea becomes particularly powerful and computationally tractable. Let us consider a graph $G = (V, E)$, where, as before, V is the set of nodes and E is the set of edges. In standard graph signal processing, each node is assigned a scalar or vector signal. However, in the sheaf-theoretic framework, we go a step further: we associate to each node and each edge a vector space — referred to as a stalk. These stalks can have different dimensions, representing the fact that data at different parts of the graph may reside in different local feature spaces.

Formally, a sheaf F over a graph G (as shown in Figure 2-8) is defined by:

- A vector space $F(v)$ assigned to each node $v \in V$
- A vector space $F(e)$ assigned to each edge $e \in E$
- A pair of linear maps $F_{v < e} : F(v) \rightarrow F(e)$ called restriction maps, defined for each node-edge incidence $v < e$, meaning that node v is incident to edge e .

Figure 2-8: Pictorial representation of a sheaf on graphs.

These restriction maps express how local semantic information at the nodes is related to shared information at the connecting edges. The consistency between node data across an edge is evaluated through these maps. The goal of this section is to learn both the graph structure and these restriction maps directly from observed data.

Central to the learning process is the sheaf Laplacian, denoted L_F . It generalizes the classical graph Laplacian and acts on 0-cochains, which are collections of vectors (one per node) from the stalks $F(v)$. These 0-cochains represent the observed signals. The sheaf Laplacian is constructed using the coboundary map δ , which encodes the action of restriction maps along each edge. Specifically, for each edge $e = (u, v) \in E$, the coboundary operator maps the pair of node vectors $x_u \in F(u)$ and $x_v \in F(v)$ to a residual vector:

$$\delta(x)_e = F_{u < e} x_u - F_{v < e} x_v.$$

This measures the disagreement between node values when projected onto the shared edge space. The sheaf Laplacian is then given by:

$$L_f = \delta \delta^T.$$

It acts analogously to the standard Laplacian: if $x^T L_f x$ is small, it indicates that the signal x is locally consistent across the graph under the sheaf structure.

Learning Problem: Given a set of observed signals $X = [x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(N)}]$, where each column $x^{(n)}$ is a 0-cochain (i.e., one signal snapshot), the goal is to learn:

- The graph structure (which nodes are connected);
- The restriction maps $F_{v < e}$ so that the total variation of the data is minimized.

Total variation in this context measures how semantically inconsistent the signal is across all edges:

$$TV(X) = \text{tr}(X^T L_F X) = \sum_{e \in E} \|F_{u < e} x_u - F_{v < e} x_v\|^2,$$

Thus, the learning problem can be posed as a constrained optimization task: Minimize the total variation across the graph, subject to:

- sparsity constraints on the number of edges;
- normalization of restriction maps (e.g., orthonormality);
- binary decision variables indicating whether an edge exists.

This leads to a hybrid optimization problem over continuous variables (the maps) and discrete variables (the graph structure). Remarkably, we show that this can be solved in closed form for each possible edge using techniques from the orthogonal Procrustes problem, which seeks the best rotation to align two vector sets. All the mathematical and algorithmic details can be found in [DBD24].

2.3.3 Results

To evaluate the performance of the proposed sheaf-theoretic semantic representation learning framework, we conducted experiments on synthetic datasets designed to mimic real-world scenarios where data at each graph node lies in different latent subspaces and is affected by varying levels of noise. The results clearly demonstrate the advantages of learning both the graph structure and the restriction maps, particularly when compared to conventional graph learning approaches that rely solely on direct signal distances without any alignment or semantic structure. In Figure 2-9, we compare the total variation of the signal over the graph when using: (i) a conventional graph inference approach based on raw signal distances (dashed lines); and (ii) the proposed sheaf-based method (solid lines), which includes the optimization of restriction maps for alignment. From Figure 2-9, we notice that, for a fixed number of edges, the sheaf-based construction consistently achieves lower total variation than the conventional method. Indeed, the semantic alignment step is crucial for reducing discrepancies across nodes, leading to smoother representations of the signal over the graph.

Figure 2-9: Total variation versus number of edges, for two different topological representation learning frameworks.

To further highlight the expressive power of the sheaf framework, we explored a clustering task based on subspace structure. Specifically, 16 nodes were assigned signals residing in subspaces of either dimension 10 or 40, within a common ambient space of dimension 64. Although the local bases were randomly generated, nodes sharing the same subspace dimension carried a form of semantic similarity. Figure 2-10(a) shows the result of a conventional clustering method, which infers a graph using standard distances between node subspaces (no alignment). The resulting graph fails to exhibit meaningful structure or clustering, and connections appear mostly random. In contrast, Figure 2-10(b) shows the graph constructed using the proposed sheaf-based alignment method. Here, a clear two-cluster structure emerges: one cluster includes all nodes with subspace dimension 10, and the other contains those with dimension 40. Moreover, nodes within each cluster are densely interconnected, even though their dictionaries (local bases) are randomly chosen. From Figure 2-10(b), we can notice how the proposed method can reveal semantic structure (e.g., similarity in intrinsic subspace dimension) that is not apparent from raw distances. The learned graphs are not only topologically meaningful but also informative for tasks like clustering and classification.

2.3.4 Conclusions

This section introduces an efficient framework for learning the sheaf Laplacian, enabling the joint inference of graph topology and restriction maps directly from data. By embedding local observations within a sheaf-theoretic structure, the method captures semantic relationships

across a network, aligning heterogeneous data in a consistent and meaningful way. Such semantic representation learning is fundamental to SemCom, where the goal is to exchange meaning rather than raw information. The inferred sheaf structure supports this by providing a topological and algebraic model of how distributed signals relate — making it possible to design communication protocols that are context-aware and goal-oriented.

This contribution is also related to the objectives of WP4, in particular Task 4.1, which addresses reasoning and semantic alignment across distributed agents. The proposed method offers a foundation for aligning local semantic spaces and enabling interoperability between agents — a key requirement for collaborative AI and semantic-aware networking. Looking ahead, this framework can serve as a semantic scaffold for advanced reasoning, abstraction, and communication tasks, bridging low-level data structures with high-level semantic understanding.

Figure 2-10: Graphs learnt without (a) and with (b) semantic alignment.

3 Semantic compression

3.1 Diffusion model-aided distributed data compression

3.1.1 Motivation

While single-agent perception systems have become common, they inherently face critical limitations, including sensor failures, limited perceptual ranges, and environmental obstructions, which affect their reliability and effectiveness. To overcome these issues, Collaborative Perception (CP) enables multiple agents to share sensing information, thereby enhancing perception capabilities and reliability. CP typically involves exchanging information via wireless communication technologies like cellular vehicle-to-everything (C-V2X). However, current wireless communication standards impose significant bandwidth constraints, limiting practical implementations of CP. Existing CP solutions can be broadly categorized into three levels based on the granularity of shared data: raw-level, object-level, and feature-level. Raw-level CP transmits full sensor data, providing high detail but consuming substantial bandwidth that far exceeds current channel capacities (upwards of hundreds of Mbps) [CTY+19]. Object-level CP substantially reduces bandwidth by only transmitting detected objects or minimal data, but this heavily relies on individual detection capabilities, limiting overall performance gains from collaboration [SWZ+23]. Feature-level CP, which involves sharing intermediate-level features extracted from raw data, presents a promising balance between accuracy and communication overhead. Methods like F-Cooper [CMT+19] and V2VNet [WML+20] demonstrate improved accuracy using intermediate feature exchanges. However, even compressed feature-level approaches still require significant bandwidth (approximately 40 Mbps or higher), posing practical implementation challenges. This subsection introduces Diffusion model based Collaborative Perception

(DiffCP), a novel collaborative perception framework based on diffusion models, designed explicitly to address the bandwidth and accuracy challenges associated with feature-level CP [MWJ+24].

3.1.2 Methodology

Figure 3-1: An illustration of CP in IUSs.

Figure 3-1 illustrates the concept of CP for the intelligent unmanned system (IUS) and contrasts the conventional feature-level CP approach with the proposed DiffCP paradigm. The diagram presents two agents (an "ego-agent" and a "co-agent") that observe the same environment from different perspectives, each producing their own Bird's Eye View (BEV) representations. Traditional feature-level CP typically involves exchanging detailed feature information, which leads to significant bandwidth requirements, making it difficult to satisfy real-world wireless communication constraints. In contrast, DiffCP leverages prior geometric knowledge available to the ego-agent to efficiently reconstruct the co-agent's feature information using a significantly smaller amount of data. This method enables achieving feature-level collaboration while keeping communication overhead similar to object-level CP, thus effectively meeting practical bandwidth constraints. The figure specifically highlights two marked regions in the point cloud data to demonstrate how DiffCP utilizes the strong geometric and semantic correlations between different agents' views, efficiently encoding the differences between viewpoints into an ultra-low bandwidth semantic representation.

The proposed DiffCP architecture is depicted in Figure 3-2. To compress the feature-level collaborative information, our approach begins by extracting BEV features using pre-trained BEV-based perception algorithms. We embed diffusion timesteps, relative geo-positions, and semantic vectors derived from the original BEV features as conditions. These conditions guide both the geometric transformation of ego BEV priors and the infusion of additional information from the co-agent. Below, we briefly describe the main components of the framework, referring to [MWJ+24] for more details.

Data processing

In this process, the agents independently generate BEV features from their local sensing data using pre-trained BEV-based perception models. The BEV representation provides a universal, spatially consistent coordinate system that facilitates collaborative perception across multiple

agents and modalities. Each agent produces BEV feature tensors $F^i \in R^{(H \times W \times C)}$, characterized by dimensions $H \times W \times C$, representing height, width, and channel number, respectively. The dimensions H and W depend on the selected spatial resolution and region of interest, whereas C corresponds to semantic feature richness.

Figure 3-2: Overall architecture of DiffCP.

Latent BEV diffusion formulation

Inspired by latent diffusion models and transformer architectures, DiffCP operates directly in the latent BEV feature space rather than the original high-dimensional raw feature space. Let F^e and F^c denote the BEV feature tensors of the ego-agent and the co-agent, respectively. Following the typical Gaussian diffusion models, a forward noising process is applied to gradually add noise to the original co-agent BEV features F^c :

$$q(F_t^c | F_0^c) = N(F_t^c; \sqrt{\bar{a}_t} F_0^c, (1 - \bar{a}_t) I),$$

where \bar{a}_t controls the noise strength, and t denotes the timestep. During the training process in Figure 3-2(a), the noisy co-agent BEV features can be generated by the reparameterization trick:

$$F_t^c = \sqrt{\bar{a}_t} F_0^c + \sqrt{1 - \bar{a}_t} \epsilon_t,$$

where ϵ_t is a Gaussian variable.

The goal of the diffusion model is to learn the reverse denoising process:

$$p_\theta(F_{(t-1)}^c | F_t^c) = N(u_\theta(F_t^c), \Sigma_\theta(F_t^c)),$$

where u_θ and Σ_θ stand for the original mean and covariance, respectively.

To simplify training, this objective can be reduced to predicting the noise term ϵ_t :

$$L(\theta) = \|\epsilon_t - \epsilon_\theta(F_t^c)\|_2^2.$$

During inference, the trained diffusion model reconstructs BEV features starting from pure noise tensors as shown in Figure 3-2(b).

Learning to control the viewpoint

To capture the spatial correlation between the ego-agent and the co-agent BEV features, geometric priors must be incorporated into the diffusion process. A two-layer MLP network, called the *geometry embedder*, is then applied to embed the relative geo-position into a vector of length d , as follows:

$$g = GE(\Delta),$$

where Δ represents the relative position between the co-agent BEV and the ego-agent BEV geo-position. The ego-agent's BEV features are concatenated with the noisy BEV features of the co-agent along the feature dimension. This concatenation allows the diffusion model to simultaneously process both perspectives, enabling it to utilize geometric correlations directly during feature reconstruction.

Learning to incorporate collaborative information

We introduce a semantic extractor (SE) that generates a unique semantic vector from each BEV feature, which distinguishes between the perceptions of the ego-agent and the co-agent. SE typically consists of convolutional layers and MLP layers, mapping high-dimensional BEV features into low-dimensional semantic vectors:

$$v^{c,e} = SE(F^{c,e}).$$

The semantic vectors, together with geometric and timestep embeddings, are used as conditional inputs to the diffusion model. Specifically, these conditions are integrated into the transformer's adaptive layer normalization blocks, guiding the denoising and reconstruction processes effectively.

Downstream-aware augmentation

We present one solution to adapt DiffCP for a high-precision task, i.e., 3D object detection. Our experiment results reveal that the exact coordinates of 3D bounding boxes for the foreground objects rely on the significant but sparse elements of the BEV feature tensors. By transmitting only the top- K elements, at the expense of extra transmission overhead, the recovered feature maps not only retain the essential distribution of the original perception but also preserve the critical components necessary for accurate bounding box generation.

3.1.3 Main results

We adopt the backbone from [XTX+22] to extract BEV feature maps from point clouds, which is pre-trained on the LiDAR track of OPV2V dataset.

(1) Trade-off between computation time and reconstruction accuracy

Figure 3-3 visualizes the denoising procedure of DiffCP. Starting from a pure noise tensor concatenated with the ego-agent BEV, the model gradually integrates the received semantic information from the co-agent into the ego-agent's observation. This process refines the ego-agent BEV features by removing redundant information and reducing the discrepancy between the generated and target features. Using the denoising diffusion implicit model approach, five sampling steps yield the best quality for models with longer semantic vectors, while shorter vectors require more steps. The entire reconstruction process takes approximately 100 ms, which could be further reduced through software and hardware optimization in real-world deployments. Interestingly, while more sampling steps should generally improve the performance, excessive sampling steps may increase the influence of ego features. As our goal is to recover the co-agent's BEV features more accurately, redundant information from the ego-agent's BEV can negatively affect MSE scores. Therefore, a balanced number of sampling steps is necessary to avoid this negative effect. However, in practical CP, the BEV features will be finally fused into

the downstream tasks. The features generated by DiffCP through longer sampling steps might naturally facilitate the fusion of BEV features, effectively integrating the reconstruction and fusion processes into a single module.

Figure 3-3: Visualization of the reconstructed BEV features in different sampling steps.

(2) Case study: 3D object detection

Figure 3-4 presents a comparison of different CP methods by plotting the data rate against average precision at intersection over union (IoU)=0.5. It shows that traditional feature-level CP methods such as F-Cooper, V2VNet, V2X-ViT, Where2Comm, and ERMVP achieve high accuracy but require significantly large bandwidths (hundreds of Mbps), making them impractical for real-world wireless communication. In contrast, DiffCP drastically reduces communication costs, achieving comparable performance to object-level CP at only 10 Kbps, which is over 95% lower than typical object-level CP methods (219 Kbps). When incorporating Top-25 augmentation, DiffCP further improves accuracy while still maintaining an ultra-low data rate of 87.8 Kbps, demonstrating a 14.5-fold reduction in bandwidth usage compared to the state-of-the-art ERMVP model (1.25 Mbps). The figure highlights that DiffCP provides a highly efficient balance between perception accuracy and bandwidth usage, making it ideal for real-world low-bandwidth CP applications.

Figure 3-4: Performance under various data rates.

3.1.4 Conclusions

This section introduces DiffCP, a novel diffusion model-based CP framework designed to significantly compress data while maintaining high perception accuracy in multi-agent systems. By leveraging geometric and semantic correlations between agents' viewpoints, DiffCP efficiently reconstructs BEV features at the ego-agent side with minimal data transmission. The framework integrates a latent diffusion process, enabling ultra-low bandwidth feature-level collaboration at a cost comparable to object-level CP. Extensive experiments on the OPV2V dataset demonstrated that DiffCP reduces communication overhead by 14.5 times while maintaining accuracy levels close to state-of-the-art CP methods. Furthermore, the introduction of Top-K augmentation ensured that critical perception details are preserved, further enhancing downstream tasks like 3D object detection.

3.2 Goal-oriented compression with reinforcement learning models

3.2.1 Motivation

Low-delay lossy compression is a communication paradigm where the information, modelled as a sequence of symbols, is causally encoded or compressed at the encoder side and then the encoded information is transmitted (possibly with fixed or variable rate) at the decoder side at which it is instantaneously reconstructed. This compression paradigm is of great importance in goal-oriented SemCom because it ensures that the meaningful information is transmitted with minimal latency while preserving the context and intent of the message.

Unfortunately, classical information theory is built on principles that promotes compression schemes that encounter possibly long coding delays, which is not desirable in goal-oriented SemCom. This makes the study of low-delay compression problems especially demanding as they rely on fundamental limitations which are very hard to be found analytically or being numerically approximated.

In this section, we study a low-delay variable-rate lossy compression paradigm, where we consider a multiletter expression of a lower bound to the optimal performance theoretically attainable and simplify it to a single-letter expression. Subsequently, we leverage some new convexity arguments on the resulting lower bound characterization and reformulate the problem as an unconstrained partially observable DP algorithm. We then propose a model-based reinforcement learning technique that relies on the approximation in policy space [B19], to approximate the solution of the lower bound [HCS25].

3.2.2 Problem setup and methodology

We consider the discrete-time low-delay variable-rate lossy source coding system illustrated in Figure 3-5, operating at any finite-time horizon. The operation of the system is described as follows.

Figure 3-5: Low-delay variable-rate lossy compression model.

Operation: At each time instant t , the source is modelled as a Markov process (not necessarily time-homogeneous), i.e., with transition probability distribution $p_t(x_t|x_{t-1})$ and initial distribution $p_0(x_0)$, which induces the joint distribution of the sequence of random variables (RVs) $X_t \in N_n^0$. For any $X_t \in \mathcal{X}_t$, we assume that the cardinality of \mathcal{X}_t is finite. The encoder encodes the information X_t generated from the source based on the past information X_{t-1} and produces a variable-rate codeword $M_t \in \{0,1\}^{l_t}$ of length l_t and expected rate $R_t = \mathbf{E}|l_t|$. The decoder receives

the past and current codewords M_t to reproduce $Y_t \in \mathbf{Y}_t$, provided that Y_{t-1} is already reproduced. Again, we assume that for any $Y_t \in \mathbf{Y}_t$, the cardinality of \mathbf{Y}_t is finite. Formally, the encoder-decoder pair is specified by the sequence of possibly stochastic mappings $f_t: \mathbf{M}^{t-1} \times \mathbf{X}_t \rightarrow \mathbf{M}_t$, and $g_t: \mathbf{M}^t \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}_t$, respectively. We note that at $t = 0$, the encoder output is $m_0 = f_0(x_0)$ and the decoder's output is $y_0 = g_0(m_0)$. This means that no prior information is assumed at both the encoder and the decoder.

Fidelity constraint: The system in Figure 3-5 is penalized at each time instant by an additive fidelity $\{D_t \geq 0: t \in N_0^n\}$. The constraint between the source process $\{X_t: t \in N_0^n\}$ and the reproduction process $\{Y_t: t \in N_0^n\}$ is described by the per-stage, average single-letter distortion, i.e., $\mathbf{E}[\rho_t(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t)] \leq D_t$, where $\rho_t(x_t, y_t)$ is the single-letter distortion function between the information source x_t and its reproduction y_t at each t .

Performance: The system model's performance in Figure 3-5, subject to the fidelity criterion described above, can be computed by the following empirical rate optimization:

$$R_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n) = \inf_{f_t, g_t: \mathbf{E}[\rho_t(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t)] \leq D_t, t \in N_0^n} \sum_{t=0}^n R_t. \quad (1)$$

The solution of (1) depends on every possible code, which makes it very challenging to develop a globally optimal solution achieving also a reasonable computational complexity. As a result, it makes sense to pursue approximate solutions via bounds.

A well-known lower bound on (1) assuming a Markov source and a per-stage, average single-letter distortion, is the NRDF [SOS20] given as follows:

$$R_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n) = \inf_{Q_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n): \mathbf{E}[\rho_t(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t)] \leq D_t, t \in N_0^n} I(\mathbf{X}^n \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}^n), \quad (2)$$

where $I(\mathbf{X}^n \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}^n)$ is the directed information [M90] between the process \mathbf{X}^n and the process \mathbf{Y}^n , defined as $I(\mathbf{X}^n \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}^n) = \sum_{t=0}^n I(X_t; Y_t | Y^{t-1})$, namely, the sum of conditional mutual informations, and $Q_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n)$ is the constraint set:

$$Q_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n) = \{p_t(y_t | y^{t-1}, x_t): \mathbf{E}[\rho_t(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t)] \leq D_t, \forall t\}. \quad (3)$$

We note that the optimization problem in (2), is not known to be convex. In [HCS25], we show that under the assumption that the problem is fixed on the posterior distribution $p_t(x_{t-1} | y^{t-1})$ such that $Y^{t-1} = y^{t-1}$, then (2) is a convex program. Using this result, we apply Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions to deal with the dual problem of (2) and to reformulate via DP recursions using a continuous information state.

3.2.3 Main results

In this subsection, we present our main results. First, we give a new structural result that single letterizes the multiletter objective function of the optimization in (2).

Lemma 1: For a given Markov source $\{p_t(x_t | x_{t-1}): t \in N_0^n\}$, and a single-letter distortion function $\{\rho_t(x_t, y_t): t \in N_0^n\}$, the characterization in (2) can be simplified as follows:

$$R_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n) = \inf_{Q_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n): \mathbf{E}[\rho_t(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{Y}_t)] \leq D_t, t \in N_0^n} \sum_{t=0}^n I(X_t; Y_t | Y_{t-1}). \quad (4)$$

Using Lemma 1, and by denoting the posterior distribution $p_t(x_{t-1} | y^{t-1}) \equiv b_t, \forall t$, we can reformulate (4) into an unconstrained dual problem formulation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & R_{[0,n]}(D_0[y_0, b_0], D_1[y_1, b_1], \dots, D_n[y_n, b_n]) \\ &= \sup_{\{s_t \leq 0, t \in N_0^n\}} \inf_{\{p_t(y_t | y_{t-1}, x_t): t \in N_0^n\}} \sum_{t=0}^n \mathbf{E}^{b_t} [\log \left(\frac{p_t(y_t | y_{t-1}, x_t)}{p_t(y_t | y_{t-1})} \right) - s_t (\rho_t(x_t, y_t) - D_t[y_t, b_t]) | Y_{t-1} = y_{t-1}], \end{aligned}$$

where $\{s_t \leq 0, t \in N_0^n\}$ are stagewise Lagrangian multipliers.

By applying stochastic optimal control arguments and the principle of optimality [B19], the previous expression can be casted by DP recursions obtained backward in time, as follows:

$$R_n(D_n[y_{n-1}, b_n]) = \inf_{p_n(y_n|y_{n-1}, x_n)} \sum_{x_n, x_{n-1}, y_n} [(\log \left(\frac{p_n(y_n|y_{n-1}, x_n)}{p_n(y_n|y_{n-1})} \right) - s_n \rho_n(x_n, y_n)) p_n(x_n|x_{n-1}) p_t(y_n|y_{n-1}, x_n) b_n] + s_n D_n[y_{n-1}, b_n] \quad (5)$$

$$R_t(D_t[y_{t-1}, b_t]) = \inf_{p_t(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)} \sum_{x_t, x_{t-1}, y_t} [(\log \left(\frac{p_t(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)}{p_t(y_t|y_{t-1})} \right) - s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t)) p_t(x_t|x_{t-1}) p_t(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) b_t + R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])] + s_t D_t[y_{t-1}, b_t], t = n-1, n-2, \dots, 0, \quad (6)$$

where $b_t \in (0,1)$, is an information state or belief.

Note that one can directly try to solve the recursions in (5)-(6) using various approximation methods [B19]. In contrast, we have solved the implicit expression of the recursions in (5)-(6), using Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions. This result, obtained in [HCS25], offers the opportunity to develop a new dynamic alternating minimization approach which can be seen as a generalization of the Blahut-Arimoto algorithm (BAA) in the classical memoryless problem of rate-distortion function [B72]. Below we state the basic convergence theorem.

Theorem 1: For each $t \in N_0^n$, consider a fixed source $\{p_t(x_t|x_{t-1}): t \in N_0^n\}$ and a given belief state $\{p_t(x_{t-1}|y^{t-1}) \equiv b_t: t \in N_0^n\}$, obtained for a fixed $Y^{t-1} = y^{t-1}$. Moreover, for any t , let $s_t \leq 0$ and $\rho_t^{(0)}(y_t|y_{t-1})$ be the initial output distribution with non-zero components, and let $\rho_t^{(k+1)}(y_t|y_{t-1})$

and $\rho_t^{(k+1)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)$ be expressed as follows:

$$\rho_t^{(k+1)}(y_t|y_{t-1}) = \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}) \sum_{x_t} \frac{e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])} p_t(x_t|y_{t-1})}{\sum_{y_t} e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])} p_t(x_t|y_{t-1})},$$

$$\rho_t^{(k+1)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) = \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}) \frac{e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])}}{\sum_{y_t} e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])} \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1})},$$

where $p_t(x_t|y_{t-1}) = \sum_{x_{t-1}} p_t(x_t|x_{t-1}) p_t(x_{t-1}|y_{t-1})$.

Then as $k \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain that for any t ,

$$D_t[y_{t-1}, b_t, \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)] \rightarrow D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]$$

$$\mathbf{I}_t(y_{t-1}, b_t, \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)) \rightarrow R_t(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]),$$

where the pair $(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t], R_t(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]))$ denotes a point on the rate-distortion curve parametrized by s_t , whereas

$$\mathbf{I}_t(y_{t-1}, b_t, \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)) = \sum_{x_t, x_{t-1}, y_t} [(\log \left(\frac{\rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)}{\rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1})} \right) - s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t)) p_t(x_t|x_{t-1}) \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) b_t + R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])]$$

$$D_t[y_{t-1}, b_t, \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)] = \sum_{x_t, y_t} \rho_t(x_t, y_t) p_t(x_t|y_{t-1}) \rho_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t).$$

The above algorithm, can be seen as an offline training algorithm for the DP recursions in (5)-(6) with provable convergence guarantees. Moreover, it admits a stopping criterion, at the k^{th} -iteration by computing absolute value of the estimation error per time stage $T_{U_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t] - T_{L_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]$ as follows:

$$T_{U_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t] = \sum_{x_t, y_t} p_t(y_t|y_{t-1}) c_t[y_{t-1}](y_t) \log c_t[y_{t-1}](y_t)$$

$$T_{L_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t] = \max_{y_t} \log c_t[y_{t-1}](y_t)$$

with $c_t[y_{t-1}](y_t) = \sum_{x_t} p_t(x_t|y_{t-1}) \frac{e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])}}{\sum_{y_t} e^{s_t \rho_t(x_t, y_t) - R_{t+1}(D_{t+1}[y_t, b_{t+1}])} p_t(y_t|y_{t-1})}$.

An algorithmic implementation of Theorem 1 is illustrated in Figure 3-6 (Algorithm 1). Note that in this algorithm, we denote by \mathbf{B}_t the set of all elements of the discretized belief state that take values in $(0,1)$. This is precisely a discretization of a continuous information state into a finite state space.

Algorithm 1 Approximation of the Control Policy Backward in Time (Offline Training)

Input: given source distribution $\{P_t(x_t|x_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}$,
given belief state $b_t \in \mathcal{B}_t$, Lagrange multipliers $\{s_t \leq 0 : t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}$, error tolerance $\epsilon > 0$

- 1: **Initialize** $\{P_t^{(0)}(y_t|y_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}$
- 2: **for** $t = n : 1$ **do**
- 3: $k \leftarrow 0$
- 4: **while** $|T_{U_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t] - T_{L_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]| > \epsilon$ **do**
- 5: $P_t^{(k+1)}(y_t|y_{t-1}) \leftarrow (7)$
- 6: $P_t^{(k)}(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) \leftarrow (8)$
- 7: $R_t(D_t[y_{t-1}, b_t]) \leftarrow (11)$
- 8: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
- 9: **end while**
- 10: **end for**

Output: $\{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$,
 $\{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$,
 $\{R_t(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_t]) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$

Figure 3-6: Algorithm 1 - Offline training algorithm for computing the backward recursions of the functions obtained in Theorem 1; relevant equations can be found in [HCS25].

After collecting these functions backward from $t = n$ to $t = 1$, we initialize the online Algorithm 2 to evaluate the cost-to-go functions forward in time (online), and identify the optimizing distributions that can approximate the minimum in (4). The source distribution $p_0(x_0)$ and output distribution $p_0(y_0)$ at $t = 0$ are given as initial conditions for the forward computation, from which the initial control policy can be obtained from $p_0(y_0|x_0)$, hence the initial posterior $p_1(x_0|y_0)$. For each t , the best policies $p_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)$ are determined by following the best trajectory $p_{t+1}^*(x_t|y_t) \equiv b_{t+1}^*$ such that:

$$b_{t+1}^* = \underset{b_{t+1} \in \mathbf{B}_{t+1}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{y_{t-1}} R_t(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, b_{t+1}^*]) p_t(y_{t-1})$$

eventually resulting in the approximation of (4). The procedure is illustrated in Figure 3-7 (Algorithm 2).

3.2.4 Simulation studies

This section provides numerical simulations to support our theoretical findings that led to Algorithms 1 and 2. We consider an example where we assume binary alphabet spaces, that is, $\mathbf{X}_t = \mathbf{Y}_t = \{0,1\}, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n$, with distortion given by the 0 – 1 distortion $\mathbf{1}_{x_t=y_t}$.

Moreover, we consider a belief state $b_t \in \mathbf{B}_t$, that consists of a matrix comprising two “quantized” binary probability distributions drawn from the original continuous state space. We denote with N_t each quantization level per t , which leads to a belief state space \mathbf{B}_t with size $|\mathbf{B}_t| = N_t^2$, representing combinations of 2 out of N_t quantized binary distributions.

The source distribution $p_t(x_t|x_{t-1})$ at each $t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n$ is chosen such that we have:

$$p_t(x_t|x_{t-1}) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \alpha_t & \alpha_t \\ \alpha_t & 1 - \alpha_t \end{pmatrix}, \quad \alpha_t \in (0,1), \quad \forall t.$$

Algorithm 2 Forward Computation of the Approximate Control Policy (Online Computation)

Input: $\{\mathcal{B}_t : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$ of given $\{b_t : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$,

$\{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$,

$\{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$,

$\{R_t(D_{s_t}[y_{t-1}, P_t^o]) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$.

1: **Initialize** $P_0(x_0), P_0(y_0), P_1^*(x_0|y_0) = P(x_0|y_0)$

2: **for** $t = 1 : n - 1$ **do**

3: $b_{t+1}^* \leftarrow (14)$

4: Compute $P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)$

5: Compute $P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1})$

6: **end for**

7: Compute $P_n^*(y_n|y_{n-1}, x_n)$

8: Compute $P_n^*(y_n|y_{n-1})$

Output:

$\{P_t^*(x_{t-1}|y_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}, \{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t) : t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}$,

$\{P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}) : t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}, R_{[0,n]}(D_0, D_1, \dots, D_n) =$

$\sum_{t=0}^n I_t[b_t^*, P_t^*(y_t|y_{t-1}, x_t)](X_t; Y_t|Y_{t-1}).$

Figure 3-7: Algorithm 2 - Online computation of the approximate value of (4); relevant equations can be found in [HCS25].

Moreover, we choose the quantization levels $\{N_t : t \in \mathbb{N}_1^n\}$ and the stagewise Lagrangian $\{s_t \leq 0, t \in \mathbb{N}_0^n\}$. In Figure 3-8 (left) we demonstrate some results applying Algorithms 1 and 2 for $N_t \equiv N = 20$, $s_t \equiv s = -2$, and $n = 100$, and in Figure 3-8 (right) we demonstrate the convergence of Algorithm 1 for several time stages selected during the backward training.

For this example, in Table 1 we compare the time consumption of Algorithm 1 across single and multi-core processing for various N over a time horizon of $n = 100$. Our results demonstrate significant improvement in terms of the computational time complexity with multi-core processing compared to the single-thread processing.

Figure 3-8: Illustration of the rate & distortion per stage and stage-wise convergence for the time-varying case.

Core	$N=10$	$N=15$	$N=20$	$N=25$	$N=30$
1	11:59.20	58:21.99	3:10:02.22	7:28:14.57	16:01:47.46
8	2:14.15	10:38.16	32:55.82	1:21:00.55	2:47:20.54
16	1:09.80	05:59.45	19:18.00	47:07.67	1:38:51.39

Table 1: Illustration of the time consumption of Algorithm 1 using single-thread and multi-core processing.

3.3 Semantic token and feature selection for AI-native communications

3.3.1 Motivation

Joint Source-Channel Coding (JSCC) is a communication paradigm where information is directly mapped to the symbols to be transmitted over the channel, and subsequently decoded from the noisy transmitted symbols. By softening the strict layer separation of standard communication protocols, this allows the designer to jointly optimize the parameters of the source and channel coding schemes to optimize the performance for a specific task. In the context of semantic and goal-oriented communications, a common solution is *deep JSCC* [XTA+23] schemes, where the encoding and decoding processes are implemented as two NN models (called generally the *encoder* and *decoder*), while the channel is represented as additional (non-trainable) layers inserted between the two. In this way, the entire architecture (encoder, channel, decoder) can be trained end-to-end on a task-wise loss. Deep JSCC methods exploit the approximation power of NNs to improve over standard coding schemes, with a graceful degradation in performance that avoids steep declines once the SNR ratio falls below information-theoretic thresholds [XTA+23].

One issue that is encountered in deep JSCC schemes is that NN models have a fixed computational cost, which depends in general on the number of layers that are used, the width of each layer, and their cost. In the context of JSCC, this means that a trained model will provide a fixed trade-off in terms of bits to be sent over the channel or number of required operations, which is independent of the specific channel SNR or condition. In this section, we focus in particular on what we call the *communication load* of the model, i.e., the number of bits that must be sent over the channel, which are proportional to the output size of the encoder.

Practically, we may be interested in *adaptive* models, able to select the appropriate compression rate based on the input or the channel condition. This translates into having encoders with variable (dynamic) outputs, in which the amount of required bits can be adjusted to match the external requirements. To achieve this with standard NNs, multiple encoders are generally trained, each one tailored to a specific communication load. Recent works, instead, have proposed adaptive models where this selection is embedded inside the model itself.

In particular, we focus on deep JSCC schemes implemented via transformer NN models, which have been originally proposed in the natural language processing field but have become the de-facto model of choice for most applications, including computer vision (vision transformers, ViTs, [WHS+21]). Transformers work by pre-processing the input with a step known as *tokenization*, which converts the input into a sequence of (vector-valued) symbols known as tokens. For example, in ViTs, images are split into non-overlapping blocks, known as image patches, which are then projected to vectors [WHS+21]. This sequence is then processed by a series of blocks, the most important of which is the multi-head attention layer, which updates the embeddings by linearly combining all tokens in the sequence. Importantly, this operation acts by pairwise comparisons, making it amenable to modifications in the input sequence such as reordering or removals of specific tokens.

In the context of WP3, we proposed a dynamic transformer model applicable in deep JSCC scenarios [DPP+24]. The proposed model accepts an additional token as an input (that we call a *budget* token), telling the model the desired communication load to be achieved. The model then adaptively selects a subset of the original input tokens, whose updated embeddings are sent on the channel in-place of the complete set of tokens. In the AI literature, this is an example of a dynamic token selection scheme [YVA+22], which is part of the broader subfield of conditional computation [NCN+23]. The work presented here represents the first application of this paradigm to the field of goal-oriented communications.

3.3.2 Adaptive transformers for deep JSCC scenarios

We describe the setup in the context of computer vision, although the methodology is applicable to any scenario in which a transformer model is used. We assume a transmitter wants to communicate a compressed version of an image, on which a certain task has to be done at the receiver's end. Coding and transmission is implemented through separate transformer models, the encoder and decoder. An overview of the model is given in Latent topology inference.

Figure 3-9: Adaptive transformer model for deep JSCC scenarios.

After the tokenization step, the image can be represented as a set of tokens $x = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$, including the image token, a special token known as a **class token** (which is used to make predictions at the receiver's end, as described below), and the budget token. The full deep JSCC pipeline is described as the three components mentioned above – encoder, channel, and decoder, applied sequentially:

$$y = (D \circ C \circ E)(x).$$

For the encoder and decoder model, a pre-trained ViT is used as a starting point [TCJ22]. The ViT is split into the middle, with the first 6 blocks assigned as encoder, and the last 6 blocks assigned as decoder. In-between these two components, additional layers are inserted to simulate channel coding and transmission: (a) a trainable block in output to the encoder, that maps the current tokens into a set of complex symbols to be transmitted; (b) a non-trainable layer that simulates noise of a given SNR; and (c) a trainable block, symmetric to (a), that maps the noisy complex symbols back to the features as input to the decoder. Details are provided in [DPP+24].

In order to make the ViT capable of a dynamic communication load, we further insert trainable token selection layers before each ViT block, shown in violet in Latent topology inference. The purpose of these blocks is to remove unessential tokens from the current set. To do this, two additional trainable layers are applied on each token, which are called the threshold layer $l_t(x_i)$ and the gate layer $l_g(x_i)$. The first is also conditioned on the current budget token and returns a scalar threshold value. This is combined with the second layer to compute a final mask as:

$$m(x_i) = \text{ReLU}(l_g(x_i) - l_t(x_i)).$$

Tokens for which $m(x_i)$ is zero are then removed from the output of the block. As such, a sequence of token selection layers (one for each block) progressively reduces the number of tokens being processed by the model. An example (after training) for a model having five token selection layers is given in Semantic communication enhanced by knowledge graph representation learning . The technique has the further benefit of providing an explicit visualization of the most salient parts of the image for the current prediction, which is highly beneficial in a goal-oriented scenario.

Figure 3-10: Selected tokens for each block in the pipeline.

All the additional layers (token selection blocks and the channel coding layers) are trained in an end-to-end fashion with a supervised dataset – in particular, the following section focuses on the task of image classification. To ensure adaptability to variable communication loads, at every iteration of training a scalar $\alpha \in [0,1]$ is sampled, representing a percentage of the total communication load available (with $\alpha = 1$ being the original model with no token selection, and $\alpha = 0$ representing no communication). The budget token is multiplied by the α scalar, and a regularization term is added to the training to force the model to adhere to the desired budget (see [DPP+24] for details). As a result, after training the model has been trained to provide predictions with any possible budget, thus allowing the user to select dynamically the budget parameter during deployment. Further evolutions of the model will consider an automatic reinforcement learning strategy. For now, the following section describes the experimental evaluation of the proposed token selection mechanism.

3.3.3 Experimental evaluation

The experimental evaluation of the proposed algorithm is divided into two broad parts. In the first part, the token selection technique is tested in the absence of a communication channel, in order to test its capabilities of efficiently selecting the relevant tokens. In the second part, results with a simple communication channel are provided as starting point for future analyses.

Result with no communication channel: We fine-tuned a pre-trained ViT model on the Imagenette dataset for image classification [MLC+22]. For this experiment, one token selection layer is added before each block of the pre-trained model, and the technique is compared with state-of-the-art techniques for token selection and token compression: one conditional computation method (AViT [YVA+22]) as well as two standard techniques which do not fall in the category of conditional computation: distillation [ALZ+20] and Weight Subcloning [SFM+23]. The last two techniques provide a fine-tuned model with a fixed inference budget, and separate models must be trained on a range of different budgets for comparison. All hyper-parameters are chosen to make the models comparable in terms of computational cost as described in [DPP+24]. Results are shown in Figure 3-11.

The impact of token selection on inference is measured in terms of latency using FLOPs (Floating Point Operations), by testing all the possible budgets for each model. It should be stressed again that the proposed method trains a single model (shown as a continuous line), while, except ToMe, the baselines always imply a separate fine-tuning for each budget (shown as dashed lines). Results show that the approach is capable of adapting to different budget selections while at the same time giving the best trade-off between accuracy and computational power required.

It not only achieves the lowest latency when using a small budget, but also achieves higher accuracy than other approaches that require a higher latency.

Figure 3-11: Accuracy-efficiency trade-off (in FLOPs) for the proposed method compared to other baselines, in the no-communication setup.

Results with a communication channel: For this experiment, a communication channel is simulated in-between the encoder and decoder parts of the model, which adds Gaussian noise to the symbols with SNR values sampled randomly in $[-10, 10]$. In this case, we fine-tune the model by only adding token selection blocks in the encoder part, since the objective is to minimize the communication load at the output of the encoder. As comparison, we consider a standard ViT model with two different techniques to reduce the dimensionality of the intermediate tokens: a trainable autoencoder (AE) model, and a non-trainable PCA projection on the leading components. In the former case, different AEs are trained to match separate desired budgets. Results are shown in Figure 3-12.

Figure 3-12: Results with a communication channel.

All the approaches achieve competitive results when dealing with high SNR. However, when dealing with noisy samples, and thus a low SNR, the proposed approach achieves the best results, while others show a drastic reduction in performance. In addition, the proposed approach is the only one capable of dynamically selecting the communication bottleneck, while the others require training a different communication pipeline for each possible one.

3.3.4 Conclusions

This section presented a novel approach to adaptive SemCom through dynamic token selection in transformer-based deep JSCC models. By integrating token selection mechanisms conditioned on a budget token, the proposed architecture enables real-time control over the communication load while preserving task performance. This flexibility is crucial for AI-native communication systems that must operate under varying channel conditions and resource constraints. The method significantly outperforms static and multi-model baselines by training a single model capable of adapting across a range of communication budgets. Furthermore, experiments demonstrate the model's robustness in both ideal and noisy channel scenarios, maintaining accuracy where other techniques degrade. These findings mark a promising direction for building intelligent and resource-aware SemCom systems.

3.4 RIS-enhanced semantic compression

In this section, we investigate the joint optimization of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) and SemCom systems, focusing on leveraging SemCom to reduce the complexity associated with RIS. We focus on the semantic encoding of KGs to serve as a universal representation of multimodal data. The embeddings of KGs in a latent space are modulated as semantic symbols for transmission. Subsequently, the receiver decodes and infers the KG structure and attributes.

3.4.1 RIS-aided semantic communication

The transition from 5G to 6G will stimulate multiple novel technology breakthroughs, among which the creation of intelligent and programmable physical and digital environments to provide ubiquitous wireless intelligence as a service [MBR+23]. A new concept called programmable wireless environments has emerged based on RISs, which are large, nearly passive surfaces made of reconfigurable elements that can control radio wave propagation. By adjusting the phase of incoming signals, these elements can reflect or scatter waves in ways that do not follow Snell's law, enabling dynamic control over the wireless channel. This leads to the idea of "wireless environment as a service." The performance of RIS-assisted systems operating this way depends mainly on two factors: surface size and structure, and phase shift precision. Larger surfaces can redirect more energy, with channel gain scaling with the square of the number of elements, assuming optimal conditions. However, this must offset inherent path loss in RIS-based links. Phase shift precision is influenced by the quantization level and the accuracy of Channel State Information (CSI). Finer quantization allows more accurate phase alignment, while outdated or partial CSI can degrade performance due to misaligned phase shifts. Acquiring up-to-date CSI for large RISs also requires significant time, frequency, and energy resources.

Recent studies have explored the integration of RISs into SemCom systems. One line of work enhances text and image transmission by using RIS to improve channel conditions and optimize the allocation of semantic features, often guided by reinforcement learning based on channel state and user needs [SCP+23]. In multi-user scenarios, research has focused on efficient RIS resource allocation that accounts for user priorities. Other approaches combine distributed RISs with probabilistic SemCom, addressing semantic-aware optimization problems under practical system constraints [JWJ+24]. Additionally, a hierarchical framework has been proposed, where RIS configuration and semantic model training are jointly optimized [MLL+24].

The proposed contribution, published in [HMS+25], harnesses SemCom to relax stringent physical layer constraints, thereby enhancing flexibility, efficiency, and performance in practical implementations. By employing a SemCom system grounded in KG representation learning, fewer reflecting elements of the RIS are needed to infer the KG and subsequently its equivalent text, compared to traditional encoding methods. This reduction in required elements potentially lowers overall power consumption, channel estimation costs, etc., thereby preserving energy efficiency. Furthermore, the semantic approach necessitates fewer bits for the quantization of phase beamforming of the RIS reflecting elements. Therefore, this section takes the complementary perspective on RIS-aided communications, with SemCom representing a means for overcoming RIS limitations.

3.4.2 Overview of the proposed methodology

SemCom establishes a dual communication channel comprising semantic and wireless components. The combined effect of these channels on input data can be modelled as a series of transformations within the semantic space, shaping the output of the semantic decoder. The nature and performance of these transformations depend on factors such as the communication environment, side information, composition with other transformations, estimation cost, system architecture, and reconfiguration overhead. This section focuses on exploring the disjoint effect of wireless channels shaped through RISs within the context of communicating the semantic representation of KGs. In the following, we expand on the characteristics of the semantic transformations entailed on KG data and the wireless transformations induced by the RIS, pictured by our system model in Figure 3-13.

Figure 3-13: System model of semantic representation learning on graphs via RIS.

Graph-based semantic communication

One key aspect of SemCom entails compressing knowledge representation. Here, we follow the semantic system introduced in Section 2.2 of [HDS24].

Semantic encoder: The semantic encoder architecture is a sequence of a pre-trained LLM encoder and a GNN that represents the input knowledge graph in semantic latent space. The pre-trained LLM generates the embedding vectors of the textual attributes associated with nodes and relations within the graph. Afterward, the GNN compresses those embedding vectors into a matrix with the number of rows equals to the number of nodes, and the number of columns equals to the embedding dimension.

Channel encoding: The channel encoder block involves a FNN followed by a power normalization layer. The channel encoder modulates each low dimensional vector encoded by the semantic encoder as complex symbols. Upon reception, the channel decoder decodes the matrix of received symbols into the semantic representation latent space matrix through an FNN architecture.

Semantic decoder: Two sub-modules of the semantic decoder are combined to infer the KG from the low-dimensional latent space matrix where each row of is a vector associated with a node. The node classification mechanism is modelled as an MLP classifying distinct low-dimensional vectors, assigning each of them to a specific node descriptor. In conjunction, the relation decoder, comprising a vanilla transformer encoder with a classification head, discerns the adjacency matrix of from the received latent space matrix, along with the textual attributes associated with the inferred edges.

RIS-aided communications

RIS improve wireless connectivity by shaping propagation paths, even when Line-of-Sight (LoS) links are blocked. A passive RIS reflects signals in intended directions, providing beamforming gain to mitigate multiplicative path loss. While this gain is theoretically proportional to the square of the number of RIS elements, practical implementations face challenges such as phase quantization, hardware imperfections, and channel estimation errors. In this section, we assume direct communication with no LoS component, and we hypothesize that the direct link between the transmitter and receiver is absent.

3.4.3 Evaluation study

This section presents numerical results to evaluate the gains offered by the semantic model based on KG representation learning over traditional encoding methods (Huffman and 6-bits) in RIS communication scenarios, assuming the absence of a direct LoS path between the transmitter and receiver. We simulate a two-stage system that leverages the semantic model and the RIS to optimize the wireless environment, the interested reader is referred to [HMS+25] for more implementation details.

Figure 3-13 shows semantic textual similarity versus RIS active elements ratio for one (Figure 3-14 (a)), two bits (Figure 3-13 (b)) and no phase quantization (Figure 3-13 (c)). To compute semantic textual similarity, we generate embeddings for both the text inferred from the decoded noisy KG and the original text. We then calculate the similarities between these embeddings using the cosine similarity metric. Figure 3-14 shows the ratio of the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) score over maximum BLEU versus RIS active elements ratio for one (Figure 3-14 (a)), two bits (Figure 3-14 (b)) and no phase quantization (Figure 3-14 (c)). The BLEU score is limited to measuring token overlap between inferred texts and reference texts, rather than assessing the actual meaning of the text. Both Figure 3-13 (a) and Figure 3-14 (a) show that, given a phase quantization precision of one-bit, the proposed semantic method achieves its optimal performance for 55% active RIS elements, while the traditional encoding methods fail to achieve an acceptable performance for 100% active elements. Figure 3-13 (b) and Figure 3-14 (b) show that the semantic model requires 20% less active elements to achieve its optimal performance for two bits over one bit phase quantization. Figure 3-13 (c) and Figure 3-14 (c) show that the semantic encoding scheme needs only 20% RIS active elements to reach its optimal performance for no phase quantization. In those settings, the Huffman encoding approach slightly achieves this optimal performance for 100% RIS active elements in terms of the semantic textual similarity, while the BLEU score is 14.5% higher for the semantic approach compared to the Huffman encoding method for 100% RIS active elements.

At the KG data level, Figure 3-15 shows the F1 score measuring the accuracy of graphs inference versus RIS active elements ratio for one (Figure 3-15 (a)), two bits (Figure 3-15 (b)) and no phase quantization (Figure 3-15 (c)). The F1 score evaluates the accuracy of triplets inference by assessing the exact correspondence between elements in the source and decoded

KGs. It measures the harmonic mean of precision and recall, reflecting how well the inferred triplet elements match the source triplet elements. Figure 3-15 validates the findings presented in Figure 3-13 and Figure 3-14 while extending the analysis beyond text applications: it assesses the gains brought by the semantic method over traditional encoding approaches in the RIS wireless settings for the broader data structure of KGs, which serve as a universal representation of data. This validation underscores the applicability of the semantic method across diverse data types beyond text in optimizing the gain of the RIS depending on its number of active elements and the precision of the phase shifts of its elements.

Figure 3-14: Sentence similarity versus RIS active elements ratio.

Figure 3-15: Relative BLEU score versus RIS active elements ratio.

Figure 3-16: F1 score of KG matching versus RIS active elements ratio.

4 Semantic data acquisition and sensing

4.1 Improving indoor localization accuracy with semantic sensing

4.1.1 Motivation

Current indoor localization technologies based on radio signals, such as Wi-Fi, Ultra-Wideband (UWB), and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), face notable limitations including sensitivity to environmental changes, high hardware and energy costs, and burdensome maintenance requirements. For example, the authors in [GGA+25] describe the design, implementation, and evaluation of an indoor localization system based on Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) measurements in wireless sensor networks, which are susceptible to obstacles, reflections, and environmental dynamics, leading to decreased accuracy. Authors in [LCK+21] leverage more fine-grained CSI information captured from the Wi-Fi devices and use deep NNs for localization. However, this method is limited by the generalization ability of the models to the environmental changes. UWB technology generally offers high-precision localization by measuring the time difference of arrival (TDoA) of signals [ZGT+24]. However, implementing UWB systems requires significant infrastructure investment and can be energy-intensive, making scalability challenging. While BLE beacons are relatively inexpensive and easy to deploy [LSC+24], they are easily affected by obstacles and reflections, leading to variability in RSSI readings and reduced accuracy [GCC+20]. These challenges motivate the shift toward semantic sensing, which enables systems to interpret high-level contextual features (e.g., user intent, activity zones, or functional areas) rather than relying solely on raw signal metrics. By leveraging semantic understanding, indoor localization can become more robust, scalable, and adaptive, reducing dependence on dense infrastructure and costly data collection. In this section, we give a semantic sensing based indoor localization approach, which integrate the localization probability map with the obtained CSI for more accurate localization performance.

4.1.2 Methodology

To facilitate accurate location estimation, we introduce the concept of a semantic map, which combines the observed CSI with a learned probability map. The overall process consists of two key stages:

- (1) **Probability map generation:** A NN is trained to generate a location probability distribution, or "probability map," based on the user's position in the environment.
- (2) **Joint estimation:** The resulting probability map is then combined with the CSI and fed into a convolutional neural network (CNN) to estimate the user's physical location.

In the following sections, we provide a detailed explanation of both stages.

Probability map generation

The main idea of this step is to generate a probability map (or heatmap) that indicates the likelihood of a user being at each grid location, given a reference point (i.e., ground-truth user location). Specifically, as shown in Figure 4-1, an indoor site is uniformly divided into K grid points, with each grid point denoted as \mathbf{g}_k ; \mathbf{g}_k can be either a 2D or a 3D vector, depending on the localization dimension. If we assume a ground-truth location x , then the estimated location can be expressed as $\hat{x} = \sum_{k=1}^K p_k \mathbf{g}_k$, given the probability map of the particular location x denoted as $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_K]^T$.

We propose to select the probability map for which the expected squared distance between grid points and the reference point weighted by probability \mathbf{p} is minimized—this only activates probabilities associated with grid points that are nearby the ground truth location. The optimization problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^K}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{k=1}^K p_k \|\mathbf{g}_k - \hat{\mathbf{x}}\|^2 \\
 & \text{subject to} && \|\mathbf{G}\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{x}\| \leq \delta \\
 & && \sum_{k=1}^K p_k = 1, p_k \in [0,1], \forall k,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\delta > 0$ can be used to trade-off accuracy vs. variance, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{C}^{\times}$ is the matrix of grid coordinates. Instead of solving the convex optimization every time, a NN shown in Sheaf-theoretic semantic representation learning is trained to approximate the mapping.

Figure 4-1: System model of location estimation given a ground-truth location.

When a reference position is input to this network, it returns a probability vector representing the estimated location distribution over the discretized grid. This probability map is then used as input (together with CSI) to the joint localizer model to predict the final location more accurately, which will be further discussed in the next step.

Figure 4-2: The trained NN for probability map generation.

CSI+ location probability map-based localization

In the second step, a semantic-assisted deep learning framework for indoor localization is further proposed using CSI and the probability maps derived from NNs. The key objective is to accurately estimate a user's 2D position in a complex environment-such as an office floor-by leveraging both physical-layer CSI and high-level semantic priors.

Figure 4-3: Joint CSI and location probability map-based localization.

Figure 4-3 demonstrates the overall structure for joint CSI and location probability map-based localization. Specifically, each user's CSI is represented as a complex-valued 3D tensor across receiver antennas, transmitter antennas, and subcarriers. The system processes this data by separating the magnitude and phase components, normalizing them, and stacking them as two input channels. In parallel, the system employs a semantic-enhanced estimation path by using the location-specific probability distribution obtained from the previous step as another input. This probability map is then concatenated with the flattened CSI representation and passed through the NN, which fuses the low-level signal features with the high-level semantic distribution. Particularly, the mean Euclidean distance between predicted and true positions is used as the loss function, which is expressed as

$$L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{(a_i - \hat{a}_i)^2 + (b_i - \hat{b}_i)^2},$$

where $x_i = (a_i, b_i)$, $\hat{x}_i = (\hat{a}_i, \hat{b}_i)$, and N is the number of samples.

4.1.3 Main results

We consider the DeepMIMOv3 simulation environment using the 'officefloor1' scenario, with data extracted from a base station labelled as 'base station 2' and user locations covering the entire office room, which spans a 34×30 meters area, as shown in Figure 4-4. Unless otherwise stated, we use the parameters given by DeepMIMOv3 website.

For the probability map generation stage, the physical environment is discretized into grid cells with a spacing of 2 meters. For training, 500 random reference points are sampled, each used to solve a convex optimization to generate a ground-truth probability distribution over the grid δ , which is set as $\delta=0.2$. A fully connected NN with two hidden layers of 128 neurons each is trained over 1000 epochs using MSE loss and Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. To verify the effectiveness of the trained network, we fed three test points which are not trained with coordinates (8.3, 25.2) m, (15.3,18.2) m, and (28.5,18.2) m into the trained model, and its predicted probability map is compared with the one obtained from convex optimization. As can be seen from Figure 4-5, the location probability maps generated by the NN reach similar results with those generated by convex optimization and demonstrate high location probability near the ground-truth points, revealing the effectiveness of probability map generation using the trained NN.

For the localization stage, a NN that learns to localize from CSI only is chosen as the benchmark, which is used to compare with the NN that integrates a semantic probability map with the CSI. Particularly, we set 16 subcarriers. The Adam optimizer is used with learning rate 0.01 and 500 epochs. The mean Euclidean distance between predicted and true positions is used as the loss function.

Figure 4-4: The BEV of the indoor scenario.

Figure 4-5: Probability map generated by a NN (upper row) and convex optimization (lower row) under different test reference points.

Figure 4-6 presents the training loss curves for the two localization models. Specifically, the blue curve shows the performance of the CSI-only model. It starts with a high localization error (above 16 meters) and gradually decreases over time, but converges to an average error slightly

above 5 meters. In contrast, the orange curve, representing the CSI+ProbMap model, starts with a lower initial error and converges much faster to a significantly lower final error (around 1.5 meters). This result demonstrates that incorporating the semantic probability map, which encodes spatial priors, significantly improves convergence speed and final localization accuracy compared to using CSI alone.

Figure 4-6: Training loss curve for both CSI-only and joint CSI+ProbMap-assisted localization.

Figure 4-7 shows the CDF of localization error for the two models. It can be seen that the orange curve consistently dominates the blue curve, indicating that it achieves lower errors more frequently. For example, over 90% of the CSI+ProbMap predictions have errors less than 5 meters, while the CSI-only model achieves this threshold for a much smaller portion of the samples. This highlights the significant advantage of incorporating probability maps in improving localization accuracy and reliability.

Figure 4-7: Localization error CDF for both CSI-only and joint CSI+ProbMap-assisted localization.

Figure 4-8 visualizes the multi-point localization inference results for the two models. The green circles represent the true user positions, while the red crosses show the predictions from the CSI-only model and the blue triangles show the predictions from the CSI+ProbMap model. The spread of predictions around the true positions reveals how accurately each model localizes users. Notably, the CSI+ProbMap model consistently estimates positions closer to the true locations, demonstrating the improved precision and robustness brought by integrating semantic probability maps into the localization process.

Figure 4-8: Test experiment for both CSI-only and joint CSI+ProbMap-assisted localization.

4.1.4 Conclusions

In conclusion, this work proposed a novel semantic-map-assisted localization framework that enhances user position estimation by integrating observed CSI with a learned semantic probability map. By introducing a two-stage process, first generating a location-aware probability distribution using a NN, and then performing joint estimation with CSI through a CNN, we aim to improve the localization accuracy leverage spatial semantic awareness. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach significantly outperforms traditional CSI-only localization methods, confirming the benefit of incorporating semantic priors. This framework offers a promising direction for more accurate and context-aware indoor positioning systems.

4.2 Time-series forecasting with multimodal data acquisition

4.2.1 Motivation

As mentioned in Section 3.1, SemCom systems can enable interesting use cases, such as CP. In Section 3.1, we have introduced DiffCP, a novel diffusion model-based CP framework for multi-agent systems. This framework provides ultra-low bandwidth feature level collaboration by exploiting spatial and semantic information. However, in this framework, we only looked at the spatial component of CP, where data coming from different agents were assumed to be timely-aligned. We know study the temporal component. In fact, timing uncertainty poses a major challenge in enabling distributed perception or CP for autonomous intelligent agents [P24]. The primary role of the perception module is to estimate the state of the physical environment, forming the foundational layer for subsequent task execution that depends on learning and inference. To accomplish this, the module operates in the digital domain by acquiring and integrating multimodal data derived from physical events and captured through various sensors. This process leverages multimodal machine learning techniques to represent the state of the world across multiple levels of abstraction [BAM18, LZM24].

Looking ahead, perception in such agents may increasingly rely on distributed sensing, where sensory data can be acquired via next-generation communication technologies, such as 6G networks. This emerging paradigm, often referred to as perceptive mobile networks [XWS+22], leverages the network infrastructure itself to sense and map the physical world into the digital domain. A prominent example of this convergence is Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) [L+22], which aims to unify wireless communication and sensing functionalities within a single, shared network infrastructure. Another key enabler is the proliferation of IoT devices equipped with various sensors, collectively generating multimodal data across a large number of distributed nodes. This data can be communicated as continuous streams, enabling real-time and CP across the network.

Multimodal machine learning is grounded in three key principles: heterogeneity, connectivity, and interactions among modalities. In what follows, we focus on multimodal data streams that exhibit temporal structure and the task of event recognition or localization [TSL+18]. A central challenge in this domain is the alignment of multimodal data, which seeks to uncover connections and interactions among elements from different modalities across time. There are three primary approaches to performing multimodal alignment [LZM24]. First, discrete alignment focuses on establishing correspondences between clearly defined, discrete elements across modalities; such as aligning words with visual objects. Second, continuous alignment deals with continuous signals, where segmentation boundaries may be ambiguous; common in audio or physiological data. Third, contextualized representation-based alignment leverages representation learning to embed multimodal inputs into a shared latent space, where alignment is implicitly captured through learned cross-modal dependencies and interactions. Recent approaches often utilize transformer-based architectures to learn such aligned spaces.

However, timing uncertainties in registering physical events across spatially distributed devices, coupled with cumulative delays from processing and transmitting multimodal data, present significant challenges for designing perception modules that depend on alignment across distributed and communicated data streams. Within this context, we identify three primary categories of delay sources that contribute to these challenges.

First, during multimodal data acquisition, each modality may experience inherent acquisition delays due to the finite speed of information propagation and relativistic effects [G09, P24]. For example, in a distributed setup, audio transmission is constrained by the speed of sound, whereas video is limited by the speed of light.

Second, due to heterogeneity, sensing modalities are inherently asymmetric. They differ in storage demands, processing pipelines, spatial and temporal resolutions, and are affected by distinct sources of noise and interference.

Third, dynamic network conditions—such as latency, congestion, and jitter—further aggravate temporal misalignment. Modalities may arrive at the perception module asynchronously and with time-varying delays. Imperfect clock synchronization among distributed sensing nodes further complicates precise temporal alignment.

The combined effects of acquisition delays, modality asymmetry, and asynchronous reception complicate the reliable establishment of temporal ordering and causality between physical and digital events across distributed multimodal data streams [P24]. In the absence of precise clock synchronization, solutions based solely on physical timestamping become unreliable, rendering cross-modal temporal comparisons either ambiguous or meaningless. Furthermore, existing alignment techniques are typically not designed to accommodate delayed or asynchronous inputs, particularly from networked streams that lack synchronized clocks. This is especially problematic when dealing with multimodal sensor data that is continuously transmitted and unlabelled. These challenges underscore the urgent need for a comprehensive characterization of temporal perception and the development of novel solutions capable of efficiently processing distributed, communicated multimodal data streams in real time, while ensuring both temporal order and the preservation of causality.

4.2.2 Blocking and immediate inference approaches

Two common synchronous approaches for performing inference on perception derived from distributed multimodal data streams are blocking inference and immediate inference [LHR+21]. These approaches are considered synchronous because they align inference execution with the arrival of data streams.

Blocking inference occurs when the system waits for the slowest data stream to arrive before proceeding with the inference process. Once all data has been received, temporal ordering can

be explicitly addressed without the need for physical timestamps by using techniques for alignment [LZM24]. As ISAC and IoT devices often collect continuous signals, we focus on continuous alignment techniques such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), manifold alignment, Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), and more recent deep learning-based extensions of these methods [LHR+21, LZM24]. These latter approaches are particularly effective in handling high-dimensional data and improving alignment accuracy. It is important to note that these techniques rely on the underlying statistical assumption that the modalities share a joint distribution that evolves over time but is unknown. However, the main drawback of blocking inference is that its real-time performance is significantly constrained by network delay factors, with inference latency ultimately being dictated by the slowest data stream.

Immediate inference, or inference without waiting, occurs when the system operates solely according to predefined arrival of inference deadlines that are independent of the availability of data streams. The system performs inference using the data available up to the given point in time in which inference is requested. In this approach, discrepancies between data streams are typically either discarded or crudely compensated for by padding the data. Similar to blocking inference, however, temporal alignment is still necessary for the partial data using the explicit, continuous techniques mentioned earlier. The trade-off of this approach is a potential reduction in inference accuracy due to partial data, in exchange for meeting strict inference latency constraints imposed by the task's inference deadlines.

Both approaches can benefit from various optimizations designed to consistently reduce the inference latency imposed by the slowest stream. One such optimization is the use of SemCom, which could reduce the required bandwidth by transmitting data using semantic features, as presented in Section 3.1. Another optimization could focus on designing resource allocation to address the effects of multimodal asymmetry and heterogeneity. A third optimization might involve simplifying the processing and communication pipelines, for instance, by leveraging the ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC) framework.

As discussed in [P24], these optimizations aim to mitigate fixed and predefined delays, thereby improving the speed of fully receiving the slowest stream in blocking inference and increasing the availability of partial data in immediate inference. However, it is important to note that simply accelerating data availability does not directly address the challenge of maintaining temporal ordering and causality, as distributed sensing nodes may still disagree on the sequence in which events are detected. More critically, these issues are still addressed in a blocking manner, as the explicit, continuous time-alignment algorithms used do not adapt to asynchronous inputs. They require the reception of complete or partial data to function accurately, inherently relying on batch processing.

In conclusion, neither approach sufficiently meets the task's quality-of-service requirements, as inference latency is constrained by the slowest data stream. This limitation has motivated the adoption of non-blocking inference methods.

4.2.3 Non-blocking inference

In contrast to synchronous approaches, non-blocking—or opportunistic—inference operates fully asynchronously once an inference deadline is specified. It strikes a balance between blocking and immediate inference by leveraging partial observations to improve multimodal inference performance and reduce latency, without necessarily waiting for additional data to arrive.

In [LHR+21], the authors introduce the low-latency speculative inference framework as the first such approach. The framework comprises three modules. The first, here referred to as the speculative module, imputes data from slower streams using fully received faster streams, guided by learned world models. In this approach, the world models are a composition of Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (CGANs), which are trained on features extracted from the fusion layer of a pre-trained multimodal model designed for the inference task. The second module, referred to as the rollback module, evaluates speculation both post-hoc and in real-

time, adaptively balancing the amount of partial data required from the slower streams based on world model uncertainty, network conditions, and the locally estimated historic performance of the task at hand. The third module, the temporal alignment module, utilizes the world models trained across diverse data profiles and network delay configurations. This module iterates through the possible world models to identify the one that provides the best alignment result, then generates the slower streams based on this model. Therefore, delayed or partially available data is treated as missing data.

Thus, the time-ordering issue is implicitly mitigated through data imputation models that infer missing information by leveraging the full availability of faster modalities and the partial availability of slower ones—a process referred to as translation in the multimodal taxonomy [LZM24]. Note that this approach strongly relies on the assumption that a paired or pre-aligned training dataset is available for training world models, that is, one dataset free from delays caused by modality asymmetry and asynchrony. However, in practice, acquisition delays are often not fully compensated for, and classical alignment methods typically target only these idealized conditions. Moreover, because of this implicit solution to the problem based on imputation, the low-latency speculative inference framework does not make use of explicit, continuous alignment techniques when operating, such as the ones based on DTW and CCA.

Recently, in [W+24], the authors enhanced the low-latency speculative inference framework, naming their non-blocking inference method AdaFlow. They introduce two key improvements. First, they propose an imputation scheduler to control which slower data streams should be imputed, based on the correlation between modalities and the task at hand. This can be viewed as evaluating the importance of each modality for a specific task, where imputation follows the degree of importance of each modality. This method is based on a graph that captures the correlation among different modalities. Second, they improve the world models by employing one-size-fits-all attention-based conditional generative networks (ACGANs), which overcome some limitations of CGANs used in low-latency speculative inference. CGANs have fixed inputs and do not account for the importance of individual modalities, whereas the attention mechanism in ACGANs dynamically prioritizes modality relevance, and they can accept flexible inputs.

Critics

The previously described approaches assume that the inter-modality delay evolves slowly and can be treated as static, which leads to a good justification for using an iterative method to identify the most appropriate world model for a given data profile and delay configuration when performing implicit time alignment. Consequently, the authors of low-latency speculative inference claim that their method addresses the temporal ordering problem in an implicit and online fashion. However, we argue that this claim does not hold in very dynamic conditions. The reliance on an iterative approach is suboptimal and may eventually lead to a poor resolution to the time ordering problem, as delays can vary significantly due to the dynamic time uncertainty in capturing events, and the inherent variability in processing times, transmission rates, and network conditions—particularly in mobile environments.

Furthermore, the current approaches treat the network as a black box, implicitly assuming First-In-First-Out (FIFO) delivery for each modality and communication channel, akin to the behaviour of protocols like the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). Note that the FIFO delivery assumption helps prevent intra-modality time misalignment. However, [LHR+21] appears to overlook this aspect by also considering the use of the User Datagram Protocol (UDP), which does not guarantee FIFO delivery. As a result, time misalignment can occur even within the same modality, which is not properly addressed by the paper. Another class of protocol of interest is the Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP), which is a network protocol designed for delivering audio and video over IP networks in real-time. However, RTP relies on synchronized clocks among devices to align different streams.

Inspired by how the human brain encodes and calibrates time [P24], maintaining a separate world model for every possible data and delay profile is both inefficient and energy-intensive.

For example, in [LHR+21], the authors trained 200 CGANs and performed an exhaustive search to select the most suitable model for each simulation scenario in a speech recognition task. Moreover, it is overly simplistic to assume that temporal ordering can be resolved solely through implicit methods, as these approaches presuppose the prior availability of temporally aligned data. How is such aligned data obtained in the first place?

To address these limitations, we propose exploring a different class of solutions that also explicitly tackle the temporal ordering problem. Before doing so, however, we take a closer look on the limitations of the low-latency speculative inference framework to better contextualize our contributions.

4.2.4 A closer look

AVE dataset

To motivate our discussion, we consider an audio-visual event localization task using the Audio-Visual Event (AVE) dataset [TSL+18]. The AVE dataset contains over 4,000 10-second video clips spanning 28 diverse audio-visual event classes (e.g., dog barking, baby crying) and various domains (e.g., human activities, object sounds). Each video is annotated with ten event labels—one per second—such that each 1-second segment is associated with a single physical event.

The videos are a subset of Google’s AudioSet, sourced from YouTube and primarily recorded using smartphones or digital video cameras equipped with built-in cameras and microphones. The native resolution of these videos ranges from 360p to 720p, with a frame rate of 30 frames per second (FPS), while the audio is originally sampled at 44.1 kHz. For feature extraction, the data is resampled to 16 FPS for video and 16 kHz for audio, with audio encoded in 16-bit signed PCM format and a mono channel.

A typical multimodal machine learning architecture

Figure 4-9 illustrates a typical multimodal machine learning pipeline for the task of audio-visual event localization [TSL+18]. The process begins with a pre-processing stage, where each stream is segmented and feature engineering is applied to extract the most informative input features from raw sensing data for subsequent learning. For audio, spectrograms based on Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) are commonly used, while video is typically encoded using the Motion Joint Photographic Experts Group (MJPEG) format, where each frame is independently compressed as a JPEG image. These encoding choices are often driven by the ease of leveraging large pre-trained models readily available online and other factors, like reducing the redundancy in audio data presenting in its waveform representation. In standard datasets, audio and video streams are typically segmented into intervals ranging from 100 milliseconds to one second, with the choice largely guided by the characteristics of the available datasets and the specific requirements of the task. Therefore, the continuous data streams are discretized and interpreted by the model as discrete elements across time. For example, in the context of the AVE dataset, each one-second segment of audio and video is associated with a single class label.

Figure 4-9: A typical multimodal machine learning architecture for audio-visual event localization when considering one audio and video stream.

Next, unimodal feature extraction is carried out, typically using pre-trained models that are often derived from or inspired by computer vision architectures. This is followed by a co-attention layer, a type of cross-modal coordination, which aims to exploit cross-modal connections to extract richer representations, such as through audio-guided visual attention mechanisms, as demonstrated in [TSL+18]. In the sequel, a per-modality temporal modelling layer is introduced to capture the temporal dynamics within each stream by exploiting temporal correlation, typically using sequence models such as networks with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) units. In the AVE dataset, temporal modelling captures correlations across different 1-second segments for each modality, spanning the 10-seconds video clips.

After acquiring these rich, jointly learned audiovisual spatiotemporal features, a fusion layer integrates information from both modalities, enabling more robust predictions by leveraging supplementary and complementary information and providing resilience in cases where one modality is missing [LZM24]. For classification tasks, a classification head is appended to the end of the pipeline; more generally, a task-specific layer is added depending on the inference objective.

For the audio-visual event localization task, the dataset used to train the architecture shown in the figure, such as the AVE dataset, is assumed to contain paired data points based on statistical co-occurrence. In the AVE dataset, each 1-second segment of audio is aligned with its corresponding 1-second segment of video, captured by video cameras with built-in microphones and stored in containers (e.g., MP4) that include presentation timestamps. These timestamps are used to recover the temporal alignment between the modalities. As a result, no temporal alignment module is required during end-to-end training of the model in Figure 4-9, as alignment is ensured during dataset curation. However, to motivate the following discussion, we assume that the audio and video streams are decoupled and virtually acquired by distributed sensing nodes, thereby losing their initial temporal alignment due to asymmetry and asynchrony. Note that acquisition delays do not change with respect to the original dataset.

On the limitations of low-latency speculative inference

Figure 4-10 provides a high-level overview of the low-latency speculative inference framework for audio-visual event localization, which operates under several key assumptions. For clarity of exposition, we define a physical event as a 10-second video clip from the AVE dataset, with each second corresponding to a distinct sub-event.

Figure 4-10: Low-latency speculative inference framework for audio-visual event localization.

First, the figure assumes that audio and video streams are continuously transmitted, and that inference windows, defined at the perception module comprising the multimodal pipeline, are not aligned with specific event occurrences. These windows are asynchronous and event-agnostic, meaning inference can begin at any arbitrary time and is not triggered by the occurrence of specific physical events. Note that the streams coming from the sensing nodes is unlabelled.

Second, it is assumed that the fastest stream (audio) is transmitted quickly enough that a complete audio segment is received within an inference window, potentially resulting in long periods of silence. In contrast, the slowest video stream is also transmitted continuously, but the content observed within a single inference window may span multiple distinct events. While this is theoretically possible for audio, the assumption of sufficiently high bandwidth—and the resulting long silence periods—makes such occurrences less likely given the strong set of assumptions made.

Finally, the framework assumes that an inference round begins as soon as the full audio stream is received, using it to initiate inference processing before the transmission of the slowest video data stream is complete. Note that an inference round differs from an inference window. The former refers to the specific instant when data streams are inputted to the model, while the latter denotes the period during which an inference is requested by an external process. The end of an inference window can be interpreted as a hard inference deadline. For the AVE dataset, each inference window spans 10 seconds plus a fixed delay, reflecting the duration of the video clips and an additional component introduced by the finite rates of data acquisition, transmission, and processing. Since the data is not collected in real time, this delay is considered negligible. Multiple inference rounds may occur within a single inference window, as elaborated below.

In the figure, the communication network is not depicted and is treated as a black-box. However, the network impacts the operation of the system by changing the time in which the streams are received. Let R_a and R_v be the rates in bits per second at which the audio and video streams are being transmitted, respectively. The times that take to receive the audio and video streams can be computed as:

$$T_a = \frac{D_a}{R_a} \quad \text{and} \quad T_v = \frac{D_v}{R_v},$$

where D_a and D_v are the size of the audio and video data sent after an inference window begins. The framework defines the delay between the video and the audio data streams as being the number k of video frames of interest to a particular event, which is unknown, received until the audio stream is fully received, being this value a function of R_v and k corresponds to a part of D_v . We further emphasize the importance of FIFO delivery of digital events per stream and per communication channel, as highlighted in [P24]. This requirement is critical to preserving the temporal integrity of each modality. However, this aspect was not sufficiently addressed in [LHR+21]. Without FIFO guarantees, the network may introduce intra-modality misalignments, further complicating temporal synchronization across modalities.

The first inference round begins by feeding the available data—comprising the complete audio stream and a partial video stream—into the multimodal pipeline. Upon reaching the temporal alignment module, as the true delay k is unknown, the module generates d candidate sequences of synthetic feature maps, each spanning the missing video frames required to complete the 10-seconds inference window. These synthetic sequences are produced using a set of CGAN-based world models, each pre-trained offline for a specific delay configuration in d . The module then selects the candidate sequence that best correlates with the audio-only feature map sequence, leveraging the temporal modelling capabilities present in the upstream pipeline. This process yields an estimated optimal delay k^* , which is used to generate a speculative sequence of feature maps and a corresponding prediction, concluding the current inference round for now.

It is important to note that k^* may differ from the true k , since the continuously transmitted, event-agnostic video stream may contain content unrelated to the target event inferred from the isolated audio stream. The authors suggest that once k^* is identified, it can be reused for subsequent inference windows under the assumption of static network conditions.

Following the initial inference round, the rollback module assesses whether the speculative prediction meets the desired accuracy threshold by tracking past prediction performance. If the accuracy is sufficient, the speculative prediction is accepted. Otherwise, the module estimates the number of additional video frames required to improve accuracy and predicts the time needed to acquire them, taking into account current network bandwidth conditions. The rollback module then discards—or “rolls back”—the speculative prediction and initiates a new inference round once the additional frames are received. This process repeats iteratively until the target accuracy is achieved or the inference window concludes, as determined by a timeout mechanism. The inference latency is then defined as the time between the reception of a full audio stream and the output of an accepted speculative prediction.

With this more detailed understanding of how the low-latency speculative framework operates, several limitations become evident, especially in relation to our objective of characterizing temporal precision in perception derived from distributed multimodal streams. Notably, the framework’s assumptions begin to break down in tasks with shorter inference windows—where faster responses are required—and under more dynamic or constrained network conditions.

First, when inference windows are shortened or network bandwidth is heavily constrained, the assumption that the fastest stream—audio in our toy example—can be fully received within a single window no longer holds. This issue is exacerbated by shorter silence periods. Consequently, the premise that temporal alignment can be implicitly resolved using the proposed method becomes increasingly fragile, as even the fastest stream may be incomplete and contain segments unrelated to the target event. This undermines the temporal consistency of the framework. Moreover, if the fastest stream is also partial, additional world models must be trained to accommodate this condition, and a more robust definition of delay becomes necessary, since the original framework defines delay based on the end of the reception of the fastest stream—an approach that may no longer be valid under such constraints.

Second, instead of actively and explicitly preventing temporal misalignment, the framework passively tolerates it, attempting to correct it through speculative inference based on a strong assumption: the availability of pre-trained world models on previously-aligned data. Again, observe that these models are trained offline under the assumption of temporally ordered data; a condition that is rarely guaranteed in real-time, distributed environments. This creates a fundamental mismatch between training and deployment conditions. Additionally, as mentioned, the training process assumes full availability of the fastest modality, which may not hold in many practical scenarios. When only partial data from the fastest stream is available, accommodating such cases would require a broader set of world models, thereby significantly increasing the complexity of offline training and expanding the delay configuration space d .

Third, in highly dynamic environments, determining the optimal alignment index k^* increasingly becomes a blocking operation, rendering the assumption of its reuse impractical. Coupled with the issues outlined above, this further enlarges the search space as the variability in d grows.

In conclusion, while implicitly addressing temporal ordering through speculative inference is a promising direction—also discussed in [P24]—the current method exhibits several limitations that hinder its applicability in real-world scenarios. Specifically, it relies on the assumption that fast streams are always fully available and requires multiple pre-trained models per data profile and delay configuration, which is both computationally expensive and inflexible. A more adaptable approach was proposed in AdaFlow, where the ACGAN-based world model architecture allows for the integration of multiple fast streams. However, even this approach struggles when the fast streams are only partially available. Furthermore, the framework does not explicitly prevent temporal misalignment. Instead, it assumes inference windows are sufficiently long and that network conditions are stable enough to allow complete capture of the fast streams, with silence periods minimizing interference from unrelated events for these streams. The fast streams are then used to complete slow streams. However, such assumptions may not hold in dynamic, real-time environments.

4.2.5 Explicitly addressing temporal ordering and causality

From the previous discussion, it is evident that current frameworks do not explicitly address temporal ordering and causality issues. Instead, they rely on assumptions—such as the full availability of non-event interfering fast streams and globally ordered or aligned datasets for training—that makes these challenges less apparent. However, as previously noted, this approach becomes unreliable when inference windows are short or when network conditions degrade. In the following, we explore other potential solutions to address temporal ordering and causal consistency in distributed inference systems.

Probabilistic simultaneity preserving mechanisms

A potential solution to the problem is to adjust the size of the inference windows, also referred to as temporal windows of integration (TWIs) [P24], in a way that statistically ensures the inclusion of data relevant to the same physical event. The objective is to ensure that event-specific data arriving at the perception module is perceived as simultaneous. In [DSS+25], we explored this concept by designing inference window sizes that statistically preserve simultaneity, probabilistically avoiding a probability of simultaneity violation (PSV). In this work, we derived the PSV by modelling three timing components of a perception module relying on distributed multi-modal streams: 1) the physical event action time (acquisition delay), 2) the sensor computation delay, and 3) the communication delay. This framework assumes FIFO delivery for each modality and must utilize continuous temporal alignment algorithms, such as DTW, manifold mapping, and CCA, to establish accurate alignment without relying on timestamps or other protocols. While this work does not directly address the temporal ordering problem, it offers valuable insights into the limitations of inference window sizes. Specifically, it emphasizes that the inference window cannot be arbitrarily shortened, as there are lower bounds defined by the system’s specifications and the nature of the physical event being observed.

Figure 4-11 illustrates how the PSV (σ) changes as a function of the inference window size (W) when changing system configurations. The specific parameters used to characterize these configurations are detailed in our paper [DSS+25]. However, as demonstrated in the paper, explicitly modelling the PSV for a real-world task is highly challenging, as it involves accounting for numerous system-level factors and relies on many simplifying assumptions to get a closed-form expression. As a result, determining the exact inference window length is generally not feasible across different real-time systems and tasks. A more practical approach is to assume the availability of a coarse estimate of this length.

Figure 4-11: PSV (σ) as a function of the integration window size (W). *Left:* Time uncertainty dominated by the computing delays when considering that computing delays are uniformly distributed between 10 and 500 ms. *Right:* Time uncertainty dominated by acquisition delays when considering that computing delays are uniformly distributed between 0 and 10 ms. Other details regarding parameters can be found in our paper [DSS+25].

Adaptive and hybrid temporal alignment

An alternative solution is to improve the design of the temporal alignment module. Ideally, the module should be more adaptive to delays arising from asymmetry and asynchrony—that is, it should be capable of handling time-varying delayed and asynchronous inputs without relying on a separate pre-trained model for each possible delay configuration. Inspiration can be drawn from the domain of statistical streaming processing—for example, algorithms like Streaming Pattern Discovery in Multiple Time-Series (SPIRIT) [PSF05]—as well as predictive modelling techniques grounded in signal processing. In the absence of clock synchronization, network delays can be estimated by periodically measuring the round-trip time (RTT) for each modality using protocols such as ping or similar tools. Computational delays can be estimated through timestamping within the local processing pipelines at the sensing nodes. This delay information can then be used to dynamically adapt the behaviour of the temporal alignment module.

Another desirable feature of the temporal alignment module is a hybrid design that leverages the strengths of both explicit and implicit strategies for addressing temporal ordering. Implicit alignment methods excel in reducing inference latency by generating missing data; however, they typically require pre-aligned training data and a large set of pre-trained models to handle time-varying delayed and asynchronous inputs effectively. In contrast, explicit alignment approaches—whether discrete, continuous or contextualized—can provide the aligned data by recovering temporal order by exploiting statistical correlations across modalities over time, using techniques such as DTW or CCA, without relying on physical timestamps. Their main drawback lies in the need for substantial buffering, as data arriving at different rates must be held until synchronization is possible. To mitigate this, explicit alignment methods can be augmented with auxiliary mechanisms, such as lightweight network protocols that preserve or infer partial time ordering across streams.

Event-triggered inference windows and event-based protocols

Another potential solution to the temporal ordering problem is the use of event-triggered inference windows. In this approach, an inference window at the perception module is initiated only when a specific event of interest is detected. This is similar to the object-level CP discussed in Section 3.1. However, since natural events are not inherently labelled, machine learning models must be employed to recognize and label these events. This can be achieved either by enabling sensing nodes to detect events locally or by incorporating a dedicated global mechanism within the perception module—here referred to as an event crawler—that identifies candidate events system-wide by relying solely on partial data. Note that the partial data should be aligned and therefore the inference crawler should come after a time alignment module.

It is important to acknowledge the chicken-and-egg dilemma inherent in having event-triggered inference windows: inference is needed to detect the very events that are intended to trigger inference at the perception module. However, in applications where modalities exhibit high redundancy [LZM24], the primary goal of multimodal inference often shifts from event discovery to improving accuracy and robustness. In such cases, event-triggered approaches can be both effective and justifiable. Conversely, in tasks where modalities provide complementary (non-redundant) information and their interaction is highly synergistic, local event detection becomes impractical. In such scenarios, it is preferable to adopt a global event crawler, capable of detecting events using partial and asynchronous data from multiple modalities. This enables the system to trigger inference in a context-aware manner, even in the absence of synchronized or complete input streams. In general, event-triggered inference windows can be understood as initiating inference based on the detection of a potential event for inference, prompting the system to collect additional data to confirm its occurrence.

There are two main benefits of event-triggered windows. First, event-triggered inference windows help in minimizing interference among data from different events, directly addressing one of the key issues observed in low-latency speculative inference frameworks. While this approach does not directly solve the time ordering and causality problems, it creates well-defined

contexts that make it more feasible to apply temporal alignment techniques. Second, event-triggered inference windows establish implicit synchronization among nodes by creating a temporal anchor that ensures all incoming data streams are aligned with a single event—without requiring explicit clock synchronization. This temporal anchor is effective only if the system can reach agreement on the occurrence of a potential event within a sufficiently short time frame. Building on this temporal anchor, one could design event-driven protocols that ensure causally consistent and temporally ordered delivery of packets following event detection and consensus.

In the local event detection case, nodes must run an event consensus algorithm to agree on whether a given physical event is occurring. For instance, in a local event detection setting, one might imagine “closing your eyes and relying solely on sound” to detect an event—or the reverse—illustrating a scenario where each modality is processed independently at distributed sensing nodes in unimodal form. This approach is feasible when a single modality is sufficiently informative to reliably detect a potential event, allowing for local detection without the need for full multimodal input.

Our framework

Figure 4-12 illustrates a non-blocking inference system that operates using event-triggered inference windows in combination with an adaptive and hybrid temporal alignment approach.

The adaptive and hybrid temporal alignment works in the following way. The module’s functionalities are distributed across multiple stages of the perception pipeline, with the core idea of operating across different time scales. At the lowest time scale (in the range of tens of milliseconds), adaptive explicit alignment is performed upon the reception and decoding of raw asynchronous data. This early-stage alignment is designed to decouple subsequent implicit alignment from delays induced by asymmetry and asynchrony, solving the problem of having to train a world model for each delay configuration in the subsequent implicit alignment modules. The simplest form of this explicit module involves buffering incoming data while simultaneously tracking delays for each modality. Each data stream is assumed to maintain temporal order due to FIFO delivery guarantees. We then define a delay-resolving window, the size of which is proportional to the maximum of the observed delays per stream. This window bounds the search space for the explicit alignment step. Within this window, we explicitly associate buffered data segments from different streams to infer temporal ordering by making use of explicit alignment techniques, leveraging the assumption of statistical co-occurrence between modalities. After alignment, we obtain paired data that can be fed into the model.

Figure 4-12: Global event-triggered inference windows with adaptive and hybrid temporal alignment.

Following the explicit alignment step, and considering the AVE dataset with its two-time scales (1 and 10 seconds), implicit alignment can be structured into two stages to accelerate inference. The inner implicit alignment module operates immediately after the unimodal feature extraction layer. It buffers incoming paired data and completes short segments of 1 second windows. As these 1-second segments are resolved, they are further buffered for use by the outer implicit alignment module, which completes longer segments of 10-seconds.

This hierarchical structure enables timely and scalable inference by progressively composing aligned multimodal representations across temporal scales. To manage data at different stages of alignment, we define three distinct memory buffers:

- M_1 : Stores short segments (on the order of tens of milliseconds) awaiting delay resolution via explicit alignment.
- M_2 : Stores segments (on the order of tens of milliseconds) that have been explicitly aligned and can undergo inner implicit temporal alignment.
- M_3 : Stores segments of 1 second that can undergo outer implicit temporal alignment.

For simplicity in initial evaluations, we propose to disregard the full-segment classification task of 10 seconds and instead treat each 1-second segment as an independent sample. This allows us to focus exclusively on the inner implicit alignment module in the early phases, deferring the outer alignment to later stages of development.

This hierarchical alignment structure can be further enhanced through the use of event-triggered inference windows. As illustrated in the figure, a global event crawler within the perception module detects potential events using partial, early-arriving data. This mechanism supports temporal alignment by leveraging the temporal anchor established by event detection, reducing the reliance on computationally expensive alignment procedures.

For example, rather than performing resource-intensive alignment based on methods such as DTW, one can adopt a lightweight protocol that uses sequence numbers and packet generation frequency to establish a one-to-one mapping between audio and video packets. This is based on the assumption that the statistical correlation between modalities is instantaneous (co-occurrence) and sufficiently relevant to the task at hand. However, if the task requires capturing long-term dependencies or identifying causal relationships, this coarse-grained alignment is insufficient. In such cases, further implicit alignment becomes necessary to refine the synchronization across modalities.

We are currently testing the ideas presented above and plan to present in the next stage of the project.

5 Conclusions

Deliverable D3.2 introduces and evaluates the initial set of methodologies supporting semantic acquisition, representation, and compression in the context of the 6G-GOALS vision. The proposed approaches align with the project's overarching objective: enabling efficient and intelligent communication by embedding task relevance and contextual meaning into the core of the communication process.

Key contributions include the development of graph- and topology-based representation techniques, the design of diffusion and learning-aided semantic compression mechanisms, and the investigation of sensing and sampling strategies optimized for semantic utility. These components establish a robust pipeline that transforms the conventional communication process into one that is adaptive, knowledge-driven, and tightly integrated with end goals.

These findings are crucial to future deliverables, particularly in the integration of these components into the broader 6G system architecture (D4.x series) and in experimental validations (D6.x series). Ultimately, this deliverable contributes to redefining the fundamentals of communication engineering by shifting the focus from data quantity to data quality and relevance—an essential leap toward sustainable and intelligent 6G networks.

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